

**Islamic Republic of
Pakistan**

Ministry of Communications

National Highway Authority

Lowari Rail Tunnel Project

GEOCONSULT-TYPESA JV

**Draft Geotechnical Interpretative
Report**

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JOINT VENTURE

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- Appendix A.2: North Link Access Road – Alignment West and East – Geological Layout Map (Drg. No. LTP.B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_001)
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1 INTRODUCTION

Several Geological Geotechnical investigations of **Lowari Tunnel** have been performed starting from 1955 till today. These investigations were carried out for different alignments mostly for the purpose of gaining information for road tunnel projects. This report is also based on these former investigations as far as they are of interest. Site visits by Geoconsult –Typsa JV have been performed in 2003.

Northern Access Road with two small approx. 200 m long tunnels with a proposed alignment west of Ashret Gol or with a 900 m long tunnel east of Ashret Gol has not been studied by other consultants before. It has been investigated during field studies in 2003 by Geoconsult –Typsa JV. The results of this work are shown in a feasibility study [6].

2 REFERENCES

Reports:

- [1] ECIL Design: Design Report (Draft), July 2003
- [2] ECIL Design: Tender Drawings, Volume-III-B, March 2003
- [3] Geoconsult-Typsa JV: Design Review Report, August 2003
- [4] Geoconsult-Typsa JV: Recommendations, August 2003
- [5] Geoconsult-Typsa JV: Additional Design Services – Inception Report
- [6] Geoconsult-Typsa JV: Additional Design Services - Feasibility Study – North Link Access Road, December 2003
- [7] LTO: Maps with location of test pits and adits (no date)
- [8] PRC: Geological Report, December 1987
- [9] SWECO: Final Feasibility Study and Design Review, Final Report, May 1995
Volume IV, Geological Report
- [10] SWECO: Final Feasibility Study and Design Review, Final Report, May 1995
Volume II, Drawings
- [11] WAPDA: Appendix to Geological Report; April 1973, Bore logs LTB-2

Geotechnical Literature:

- [12] BENDER, F.K. & RAZA, H.A. (1995): Geology of Pakistan, Gebrueder Borntraeger, Berlin - Stuttgart
- [13] HOEK, E. & BROWN, E.T. (1997). Practical estimates of rock mass strength. Int. J. Rock Mech Min Sci 34 (8): 1165-1186
- [14] HOEK, E. & MARINOS, P. (2000): Predicting Squeeze. Tunnels and Tunneling International, November 2000
- [15] ISRM Commission on Testing Methods. (1993). In Brown, E.T. (ed.) Rock Characterization Testing and Monitoring. Pergamon Press
- [16] MARINOS, P & HOEK, E. (2000): GSI: A geologically friendly tool for rock mass strength estimation. Proceedings of the International Conference on Geotechnical & Geological Engineering (GeoEng 2000), Technomic Publishing Co.Inc., p.p 1422-1440, Melbourne, Australia
- [17] ÖGG - Austrian Society for Rock Mechanics (2001): Richtlinie für die Geomechanische Planung von Untertagearbeiten mit zyklischem Vortrieb.
[Guidelines for the Geomechanical Design of Underground Works by Conventional Tunneling]

3 LOWARI TUNNEL

3.1 Alignment and Topography

The proposed alignment of the tunnel is shown on the geological layout map (Appendix A.1) and has been described already in the Inception Report [5]. It leads from the existing South Portal near Mirgha Khwar River towards Ziarat Post and has to underpass a huge mountain ridge. Because of the high elevation of mountains surrounding the Lowari Pass the overburden of tunnel will reach up to 1100 m. The topographic longitudinal profile is also shown in the geological longitudinal section (Appendix A.1)

3.2 Existing Geological-Geotechnical Investigations

Some of the previous geological-geotechnical investigations performed have already been listed in the Inception Report [5]. The following documents on existing investigations are, as far as they are of interest for the actual alignment, listed below:

3.2.1 Engineering Geological Mapping

Engineering geological mapping has been performed to a greater or lesser extent by various organisations involved in previous investigation activities (WAPDA, LTO, PRC SWECO, ECIL). Because of different investigation targets (road tunnel at low or high level alignment, railway tunnel) and inconsistent interpretation for the transition from one rock type to another some differences in geological layout maps could be found. Basically similar rock units have been distinguished and shown in geological layout maps and longitudinal profiles. Longitudinal profiles of the most recent investigations (PRC, ECIL, SWECO) do not show the geology at tunnel level.

Besides this mapping orientations of discontinuities have been measured and estimations of the strength (UCS) of rock samples have been carried out.

In earlier investigations a fault zone between Gujarat Post and Ziarat Post, parallel to the planned tunnel and following roughly the road to Lowari top has been found by surface mapping, seismic profiles, trenches and boreholes. SWECO and ECIL, who recognized the associated crushed rock, state that its existence is due to heavy glacial and fluvial erosional activity. They do not identify this zone as a proper fault, but also do not exclude altogether the possibility of such a feature. They recommend an alignment more to the east to avoid a potential fault zone. This is also proposed by Geoconsult/Typsa.

3.2.2 Core Drilling

The following logs of core drillings are available from several drilling campaigns. The locations of the bore holes are shown on the geological layout map (Appendix A) and the logs are presented in Appendices C.2 to C.5. Not all logs are readable and/or complete.

The boreholes are named as follows:

Borehole no.	Depth [m]	Ground elevation [m]	Location	Performed
LT-1	58m	2316	Ziarat, near bend in Trangar Gol	WAPDA
LT-2	63m	2438	Near Mirga Khwar	WAPDA
LT-3	91,5m	2650	Dare Khwar	WAPDA
LTB 1	Partly missing; 366,0m	2990	Daro Khwar	LTO
LTB 2	213m	2755	Dare Khwar (shaft 1)	LTO
LTB 3	Not available			LTO
LTB 4	60m	2680	North Lowari top road	PRC/EC
A	63m	2319	On ridge north of Trangar Gol	SWECO
B	72m	2329	On ridge north of Trangar Gol	SWECO
D	75m	2314	Few m south of Trangar Gol	SWECO
E	31m	2659	North Lowari top road (near LTB 4)	SWECO

Table 1: List of Boreholes

In some of the core drillings minor shear zones and up to 100% loss of flushing fluid (water) have been observed. Also artesian water has been encountered for a while in a depth of more than 100 m flowing out of borehole LTB-2 (see Appendix C.3).

3.2.3 Adits and Existing Tunnel

Several adits and trenches have been constructed to gain more information. Adits in the vicinity of the rail tunnel alignment are LTA 5 and LTA 6.

LTA 5 is situated east of Ziarat Post close to Trangar Gol river area and is still accessible. The cross section is approx. 2 m² and it is situated in the vicinity of the North Portal area of Lowari Rail Tunnel (see Appendix B, Fig.11). No rock support has been applied in this

adit. Most of the other adits, trenches or trial pits have in the meanwhile fully or partly collapsed (LTA 6 near South Portal of existing tunnel).

At the South Portal of Lowari Tunnel approximately 600 m of top heading and approximately 375 m of bench have been excavated. Excavation of this part has been performed by drill and blast method during the years 1975 to 1978. This tunnel which has been originally designed to be a road tunnel follows the proposed alignment of the rail tunnel. It is still accessible (see Appendix B, Fig.1 to 5). Most of the existing tunnel is completely unsupported and some rock wedges have fallen from the crown area in the past 30 years. The cross section of the existing tunnel is approximately 63 m².

3.2.4 Petrographic Analysis

Petrographic investigations on thin sections made from samples taken out of boreholes LT-3 and LTP 2 have been performed by WAPDA in 1973. Results are shown in Appendix C.1.

3.2.5 Seismic Analysis

Locations of seismic profiles performed by Lowari Tunnel Organisation along the road from the existing South Portal to Lowari Top are shown on a layout map, however, no results are available. It is obvious that the purpose of these investigations was to investigate the fault zone between Gujarat Post and Ziarat Post.

Shallow refraction seismic profiles by SWECO are mainly situated in river beds or on slopes near Trangar Gol. They had the purpose to distinguish between overburden or alluvium and bed rock. In the Trangar Gol area the alluvium cover above the bed rock was indicated to be up to 15m deep (Appendix C.6).

3.2.6 Remote Sensing

Analysis of satellite images has also been performed by SEWCO. Predicted faults have been shown on a map.

3.2.7 Permeability Tests (Lugeon tests)

Permeability Tests have been performed by SWECO in drill holes A and B near Ziarat Post. The location of the bore holes can be seen in Appendix A.1

Bore Hole	Ground Level [m]	Depth [m]	Max. pressure [kp/cm ²]	Lugeon *)
A	2319	57 - 60	2.8	4.3
A	2319	60 - 63	2.8	11.0
B	2329	63 - 66	2.8	2.4
B	2329	66 - 69	2.8	3.2

Table 2: Permeability Tests

*) No unit was specified in the test results. A standard Lugeon test has the unit [l/min/m] at 10 kg/cm². The applied pressure is relatively low compared to depth of tests.

Lugeon tests or field estimations have obviously been performed also by PRC, as Lugeon values are mentioned in the longitudinal section of the ECIL design report. Lugeon permeability is given with a range of <1-5 and <1-10 for mapped units.

3.2.8 Rock and Soil Laboratory Tests

Point Load tests on rock samples have been carried out on behalf of SWECO. The following point load strengths have been determined:

Bore Hole	Ground Level [m]	Depth [m]	Rock Type	Point Load Strength Index I_s [MPa]	Correlated UCS *) [MPa]
A	2319	53.1 – 60.2	Volcanic rock	2.96 – 3.00	71 -72
B	2329	33.1 – 59.7	Volcanic rock	4.25 – 8.59	102 - 206
D	2315	48.0 – 57.4	Granodioritic rock	8.16 – 11.60	195 - 278

Table 3: Point Load Tests

*) for UCS = $24 \cdot I_s$

The location of the bore holes can be taken from Appendix A.1.

Available laboratory tests like UCS tests, determination of specific gravity, porosity, adsorption, dry unit weight, modulus of elasticity on rock bolder samples have been carried out for LTB-4. Also sieve analyses and Atterberg limits have been determined on samples out of this core drilling hole. Results of these tests are shown in Appendix C.4.

In bore hole LTB-4 no bed rock has been found and only cores of boulders were available (see bore log Appendix C.4).

3.2.9 Chemical Water Analysis

Water analyses on samples of Trangar Gol and Mirgha Khwar have been performed in August 1997 (listed in SWECO report) and are shown in Appendix C.7. Low mineralization of water is typical for water of this origin. Some sulphate (<2 mg/l) and chloride (<1 mg/l) content has been detected. This amount of sulphate and chloride is not likely to be aggressive to shotcrete.

3.3 Geological Overview

The project area belongs to the geological formation of the Kohistan Complex which is situated in between the Indian and Eurasian Continental Plates. It consists of the Kohistan Batholith (intrusive rock) and volcanic sedimentary groups which usually show more or less influence of metamorphism. Due to movements between the tectonic plates regional

deformations like faulting and thrusting has occurred. Because of ongoing movement of the tectonic plates this area has to be considered as an active seismic zone.

3.4 Engineering Geological Mapping Units

Based on several field investigations and mappings the following engineering geological units can be summarized. These units are shown on a geological layout map (Appendix A.1) compiled from different former investigations and based on field checks made by Geoconsult-Typsa JV in 2003.

3.4.1 Slope Debris and Alluvium

Along the immediate alignment of Lowari Tunnel slope debris and alluvium are usually found in the vicinity of portal areas and far above the tunnel, where it is not of big interest. Detailed investigation of slope debris has been performed with borehole LTB 4 (see Appendix C.4). In Trangar Gol a thickness of 15m alluvium above bed rock has been detected by SWECO by means of refraction seismic profiles (see Appendix C.7). Alluvium consists mainly of gravels, cobbles and boulders embedded in a finer matrix. Slope debris and alluvium can be mixed with each other as can be seen in the Ziarat Post area. Temporary natural cuts induced by erosion of Trangar Gol River can be quite steep with an inclination of more than 40°.

3.4.2 Metasediment Unit

This unit contains quartzites and schists. Metasediments show different degrees of weathering on the surface. Quartzite is only slightly weathered. Schists show more intensive weathering. South of Ziarat Post weathered Schists are prevailing and form the weakest rock portion (except faulted rock) of Lowari Tunnel.

Rock types:	Schists, small portions of Quartzite
Texture:	distinct schistosity banding in Quartzite visible
Expected Quartz content:	Quartzite (>95%) Schists (<20%)
Spacing of discontinuities:	very close (2 cm - 6 cm) to close (6 cm - 20 cm)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium to high (schistosity)
Roughness of discontinuities:	low to medium
Surface of discontinuities:	stained and weathered, in parts fillings with mica visible
Weathering:	moderate to highly weathered on surface outcrops
Sensitivity to water:	sensitivity of Schists indicated
UCS of rock sample:	1 - 20 MPa (Schists) ✓ 100 - >200 MPa (Quartzite)

Above information is given for the average rock mass. This unit is supposed to be the weakest of those encountered in the project area. The presence of water will further reduce the shear strength properties of Schists.

3.4.3 Metavolcanic Unit

Metavolcanic rock is mostly exposed on the surface without signs of intensive weathering. Joints are usually only stained and sometimes open due to expansion on slopes. Sound rock is prevailing. Sheared portions are exposed south of Ziarat Post platform and show also some weathering.

Rock types:	Metavolcanic rock (banded volcanics, amphibolites)
Texture:	densely jointed, slightly to distinct banding visible
Expected Quartz content:	usually no Quartz or <10%
Spacing of discontinuities:	very close (2 cm - 6 cm) to close (6 cm - 20 cm) near Ziarat Post
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	medium to high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	fresh to only slightly weathered
Sensitivity to water:	no sensitivity indicated
UCS of rock sample:	100 - >200 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass.

3.4.4 Metaigneous Unit

Metaigneous rock is mostly exposed on the surface without signs of intensive weathering. Joints are usually only stained and sometimes open due to expansion on slopes. Sound rock is prevailing and sheared portions are rare.

Rock types:	Metaigneous rock ("Ortho Gneiss") with intercalations of amphibolite
Texture:	massive to jointed, distinct gneissic banding visible
Expected Quartz content:	>20% up to 50%
Spacing of discontinuities:	moderate (20 cm - 60 cm) to wide (60 cm - 2 m)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	fresh to only slightly weathered
Sensitivity to water:	no sensitivity indicated
UCS of rock sample:	100 - >200 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass. Due to local faulting and dense joint pattern weakening of rock mass may be encountered in short sections of rock cuts and tunnels.

3.4.5 Granite Unit

Granite is mostly exposed on the surface without signs of intensive weathering and forms steep rock walls. Joints are usually only stained and only sometimes open due to expansion on slopes. Sound rock is prevailing and sheared portions are rare.

Rock types:	Granite, Granodiorite occasionally Gabbro intersection, local small Amphibolite sills
Texture:	jointed, no or slightly gneissic banding visible
Expected Quartz content:	>20% up to 50%
Spacing of discontinuities:	moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	fresh to only slightly weathered
Sensitivity to water:	no sensitivity indicated
UCS of rock sample:	100 - >200 MPa, occasionally >250 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass. Due to local faulting and dense joint pattern weakening of rock mass may be encountered in short sections of rock cuts and tunnels.

3.4.6 Biotite Granite Unit

Exposed Biotite Granite is usually intensively weathered and not found fresh on the surface. Effect of weathering is expected to decrease with rising overburden. Only near water bearing zones alterations may also be found at greater depths. This unit is expected to be found with frequent transitions into Granite.

Rock types:	Biotite rich Granite with transition into Granite
Texture:	jointed, no or slightly gneissic banding visible
Expected Quartz content:	>20% up to 50%
Spacing of discontinuities:	moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	never found fresh on surface
Sensitivity to water:	sensitivity indicated
UCS of sound rock sample:	50 - >150 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass. Due to local faulting and dense joint pattern weakening of rock mass may be encountered in short sections of tunnels.

3.5 Structural Analysis of Discontinuities

3.5.1 Schistosity

A distinct schistosity can be observed especially in the northern parts of Lowari Tunnel in the Metaigneous unit and in Metasediments. Metavolcanics south of Ziarat Post are usually banded.

The main striking orientation of schistosity is NE - SW with dipping direction mostly towards NW or SE. Due to tectonic processes also folding may be observed and dipping is varying around the main striking direction. This striking is parallel to a regional discontinuity direction. Pole points and striking direction of discontinuities can be seen in the diagram below.

Figure 3-1: Strike direction and pole points of schistosity

Statistical analyses of data show maxima (center of gravity) for schistosity with sf 305/59, sf 161/73 and sf 119/54. See also Appendix D.

3.5.2 Other Discontinuities

Main striking direction of joints is NE – SW and NW – SE. The NE – SW striking direction is also typical for estimated faults detected from satellite images as shown in Appendix A.1. More statistical data of discontinuities related to different areas of the Lowari Tunnel alignment are presented in Appendix D.

Figure 3-2: Strike direction of discontinuities (joints and faults)

3.6 Faults

Minor faults and shear zones are likely to be found in sound and weak rock. The basis of fault estimation is the use of satellite images and the occurrence of faults in the field. The potential existence of shear zones or faults far below the surface is proved by core drillings where completely sheared rock has been detected in a depth of more than 100 m (LTB-2, see Appendix C.3).

Most of the predicted faults have a striking direction which is almost perpendicular to the tunnel axis (which is favourable), but they cannot be avoided by shifting the alignment. A possible shear zone between Gujarat Post and Ziarat Post which is running parallel to the alignment (west of the alignment, near the road to Lowari top) is avoided as the tunnel alignment is shifted towards east.

The expected orientation of faults and their occurrence at tunnel level is shown in the drawing "Geological Sections & Layout Map" (Appendix A.1).

3.7 Hydrogeological Conditions

Joints and other discontinuities of almost all rock types are closed according to investigations on surface outcrops or in existing adits and the existing tunnel at the South Portal. This would indicate only minor water inflow for the Lowari tunnel and even dry conditions are expected for long tunnel sections. Nevertheless, several shear zones are likely to be encountered during tunnel excavation which will produce some water inflow. The existing section of Lowari Tunnel at the South Portal yields water inflow of approx. 1 l/s, still 30 years after excavation.

Several boreholes of previous investigations indicate minor shear zones and in some cases up to 100% loss of flushing fluid (water) was experienced. Artesian water was encountered in bore hole LTB 2, rising from a depth of more than 100m, but disappearing after a while.

Some water ingress into the tunnel is therefore possible when crossing shear zones, even after passing long tunnel sections with dry or only moist conditions. Water ingress may occur under pressure especially if the aquifer is trapped between impermeable layers. The underpassing of the valleys of Dare and Daro Khwar will raise the probability of water ingress. In most cases water ingress during tunnel excavation is expected to decrease quickly in quantity and pressure. Short time water inflow can reach up to 50 l/s. At some of the locations the water ingress will remain as permanent inflow with lower quantity.

Expected hydrogeological conditions related to certain tunnel sections are shown in the longitudinal section of the drawing "Geological Sections & Layout Map" (Appendix A.1).

3.8 Methodology of Geotechnical Interpretation

The basis for the geotechnical design of the tunnel is provided by the specific geotechnical interpretation of the project area which is implemented by the following steps:

a) Establishment of Geotechnical Model:

By compiling all available geotechnical data an appropriate geotechnical model along the tunnel alignment is established which is characterised by the variation of relevant lithologies and geological structures. Additional information is based on the assessment of fault patterns, geotechnical characteristics of faults and discontinuities, assessment of physical rock properties, and assessment of the hydrogeological situation. The geotechnical model is summarised on the drawing "Geological Sections & Layout Map" (Appendix A.1).

b) Geotechnical Units and Rock Mass Types

The definition of Geotechnical Units and Rock Mass Types comprises a subdivision of the tunnel alignment into zones of similar tunnelling conditions (Geotechnical Units) and a detailed characterisation of distinct rock masses predicted (Rock Mass Types).

c) Rock Mass Behaviour Types and Excavation Classes

The rock mass characterisation is combined with an assessment of rock stress conditions and, based thereon, a prediction of the behaviour of the rock mass during tunnel

excavation is given (Rock Mass Behaviour Types). Typical cases of the behaviour are put into context with the definition of characteristic requirements for excavation and tunnel support (Excavation Classes). These reflect the technical provisions necessary to satisfy the rock response during tunnel construction in the given environment.

3.9 Geotechnical Units (GTU)

A Geotechnical Unit in terms of the geotechnical interpretation reflects a section of the tunnel where relatively consistent ground conditions are anticipated. Thus the tunnel alignment is divided into 9 units (Geotechnical Units, GTU) where the combined effects of the engineering-geological conditions, the initial stress situation and the ground water conditions, including their variations, are predicted to present consistent tunnelling conditions. The distribution of Geotechnical Units along the tunnel alignment is shown in the longitudinal section of the drawing "Geological Sections and Layout Map" (Appendix A.1).

3.10 Rock Mass Types (RMT)

Rock Mass Types are selected and defined according to their characteristic geotechnical features. The rock mass characterisation includes:

- characteristics of intact rock (lithology, physical properties),
- discontinuities (frequency, surface properties)
- influence of weathering,
- properties of faulted rock.

On the basis of this rock mass characterisation the significant rock mass types are defined as presented in the following table.

Rock Mass Types are correlated to Engineering Geological Units. The estimated distribution of RMTs along the alignment is shown in the longitudinal section of the drawing "Geological Sections and Layout Map" (Appendix A.1). Predominant RMTs are shown in bold letters, secondary RMTs in normal letters and RMTs of minor occurrence are shown in brackets.

Rock Mass Type	Rock type	Estimated Uniaxial Compressive Strength [MPa]		Weathering	Spacing of discontinuities [according ISRM]	Properties of discontinuities
		rock sample	rock mass			
RMT 1	Granite, Granodiorite; occ. Gabbro	>100 - 250	25 - 60	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	Clean, rough; occ. stained
RMT 2		>100 - 200	20 - 50	Slightly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	Stained, rough
RMT 3	Orthogneiss, occ. intercalations of amphibolite (Metaigenous unit)	>100 - 250	20 - 50	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	Clean, rough
RMT 4		>100 - 200	15 - 45	Slightly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	Stained, rough
RMT 5	Metavolcanics	>100 - 200	15 - 50	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	Clean, rough
RMT 6		>50 - 200	10 - 35	Slightly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	Stained, smooth
RMT 7	Metasediments, mainly quartzite	>100 - 250	15 - 45	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	smooth
RMT 8	Metasediments, Mainly schists	5 - >25	0,5 - 5	Slightly to moderately weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm), occasionally very close (2 cm - 6 cm)	Smooth, fillings parallel schistosity
RMT 9	Biotite granite with transitions to granodiorite and granite	50 - 150	5 - 40	Slightly to moderately weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	
RMT 10		1 - 5	0,5	Moderately to highly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	
RMT 11	Fault and shear zones, crushed rock of any origin	1 - 5	0,5	Moderately to highly weathered	Sheared and crushed	

Table 4: Rock Mass Types

Metamorphic Rock Mass with distinct schistosity shows anisotropic rock mass strength. Highest Rock Mass Strength is achieved perpendicular to schistosity. Weakest Rock Mass strength is given when the strike is parallel to an exposed rock surface and the major principal stress is orientated at approximately 30° ($45 - \phi/2$) to the plane of schistosity.

Estimation of rock mass strength was carried out according to Marinos & Hoek [16]. Input parameters are GSI (geological strength index), mi (Hoek Brown constant varying for different rock types) and estimated UCS (field estimations also in [16]).

For calculation of rock mass parameters the following input data have been used:

*145.03 PSI
= 1 MPa*

Rock Mass Type	UCS (intact sample) [MPa]	mi	GSI	Rock Mass Strength [MPa]
Granite (RMT 1/2)	150/100	32/29	65/35	60/20
Gneiss (RMT 3/4)	150/100	28/23	60/35	50/15
Metavolcanics (RMT 5/6)	150/50	28/26	55/35	40/10
Metasediments (Quartzite RMT 7)	150/100	20/20	55/35	40/10
Metasediments (Schists RMT 8)	25/5	10/8	50/35	5/0,5

Table 5: Rock Mass Parameters

3.11 Rock Mass Behaviour Types (RBT)

A general indication of the reaction of the rock mass to tunnel excavation is given by means of Rock Mass Behaviour Types (RBT).

Besides the rock characterisation as described by RMTs the assessment of stress conditions in the ground is equally important for the appraisal of the behaviour of the rock mass during excavation. Geological factors influencing initial stress conditions are:

- height of overburden, position of water table,
- morphology,
- lithology (changes of weak and strong rocks),
- rock structure, in particular bedding or foliation,
- geological history of the region.

By empirical methods or simple analytical models the magnitude of stresses and the rate of deformation as well as potential failure phenomena can be predicted. Besides mechanical properties of the ground the location and orientation of zones of weakness relative to the tunnel axis will influence the rock mass behaviour. The RBT does not consider the effect of support measures and subdivision of the cross section.

Rock Mass Behaviour Types are correlated to Geotechnical Units (GTU). The estimated distribution of RBTs along the alignment is shown on the longitudinal section of drawing

“Geological Sections and Layout Map” (Appendix A.1). Predominant RBTs are shown in bold letters, secondary RBTs in normal letters and RBTs of minor occurrence are shown in brackets.

Rock Mass Behaviour also depends on the size of the cross section of excavation. The cross section for Lowari Tunnel is in general approx. 45 m², but increases to approx. 73 m² for the enlarged tunnel sections of approximately 450m length in the middle of the tunnel, and of approximately 200 m length at the North Portal.

The following RBTs, defined according to Austrian Guideline for Geomechanical Design [17], are applicable to the Lowari Tunnel Project.

The typical provisions for excavation and primary support as indicated in the detailed description of the RBTs will guarantee the required stable system behaviour.

Rock Mass Behaviour Type (RBT)	Description of potential failure modes/mechanisms during excavation of the unsupported rock mass
RBT 1 Stable	Stable rock mass with the potential of small local gravity induced falling or sliding of blocks
RBT 2 Stable with the potential of discontinuity controlled block fall *	Deep reaching, discontinuity controlled, gravity induced falling and sliding of blocks, occasional local shear failure
RBT 3 Shallow spalling and shear failure mechanism, ravelling material from the crown	Shallow stress induced shear failures in combination with discontinuity and gravity controlled failure of the rock mass.
RBT 4 ¹ Deep seated shear failure	Deep seated stress induced shear failures and large deformation
RBT 5 Rock burst	Sudden and violent failure of the rock mass, caused by highly stressed brittle rocks and the rapid release of accumulated strain energy

Table 6: Rock Mass Behaviour Types

The expected project-specific rock mass behaviour is described for drill and blast excavation, assuming smooth blasting by skilled workers. Rock mass behaviour and typical excavation and support provisions are described below:

3.11.1 RBT1

Stable (intact) rock mass is characterized by the potential of small local gravity induced falling or sliding of blocks. After performing of scaling rock mass remains more or less stable. In the long term smaller portions can fall, if not supported, but overall stability will not be affected. Joint pattern is usually medium to wide and closed joints with rough surface prevail. Very small displacements of the tunnel profile can be expected, which subside soon after blasting. Presence of water has no effect on stability of rock mass.

- 4) • ~~Spot bolting and shotcrete will be required occasionally during construction. Shotcrete and wire mesh will be required for long term protection of the crown in case of close and unfavourable joint pattern.~~
- 3) • Type of excavation: Full face excavation,
Possible round lengths > 3 m.

3.11.2 RBT2

Small rock portions may fall or slide quite soon after blasting induced by discontinuities and gravity. Small displacements usually subside quickly. Joints are developed. Presence of water has some influence on rock mass stability.

- 4) • Bolting, shotcrete with wire mesh required.
- 3) • Type of excavation: Full face excavation,
Possible round lengths 2 to 3 m.

3.11.3 RBT3

Small to medium large rock portions may fall induced by discontinuities, gravity and occasional local shear failures. Shear failure propagation and development of shallow plastic zones. Displacements continue for some weeks but show a significant decrease of displacement rate after short time. Joints are well developed. Presence of water has negative effect on rock mass stability.

- 4) • Steel ribs (or better lattice girders), systematic bolting and shotcrete with wire mesh are required. Occasionally forepoling will be necessary.
- 3) • Type of excavation: Full face excavation with occasional face bolting and sealing of face with shotcrete,
Possible round lengths 1,4 to 2 m.

3.11.4 RBT4

Development of deep plastic zones. Large and long lasting displacements. Presence of water leads to further reduction of stability of rock mass.

- 4) • Opening of face (if required in sections) with immediate application of shotcrete. Use of steel ribs (or lattice girders) and forepoling necessary. Systematic rock bolting, shotcrete with wire mesh and invert are required to establish equilibrium after few months. In special cases also temporary invert, underpinning of top heading footings, face bolting, etc. may be required.
- 3) • Type of excavation: Division into top heading, bench and invert or full face excavation with long systematic face bolting,
Possible round lengths 0,8 to 1,4 m.

3.11.5 RBT5

Rock burst. Sudden and violent failure of the rock mass close to the excavated surface, caused by highly stressed brittle rock and the rapid release of accumulated strain energy. Usually in only sparsely jointed rock mass under high overburden.

- Dense short bolting and shotcrete, possibly with steel fibres, will be required for safety reasons.
- Type of excavation: Full face excavation.

3.12 Predicted Allocation of Rock Mass Behaviour Types (RBT)

The predicted allocation of RBTs for each Geotechnical Unit (GTU) is given in the table below:

Geotechnical Unit	Predominant RBT	Secondary RBT	Minor RBT
GTU 1	RBT 1	RBT 2	(RBT 3)
GTU 2	RBT 2	RBT 3	(RBT 4)
GTU 3	RBT 2	RBT 1	(RBT 3, RBT 4)
GTU 4	RBT 3	RBT 2, RBT 4	-
GTU 5	RBT 2	RBT 1, RBT 5	(RBT 4)
GTU 6	RBT 3	RBT 2	(RBT 4)
GTU 7	RBT 1	RBT 2	(RBT 3)
GTU 8	RBT 3	RBT 2	(RBT 4)
GTU 9	RBT 3	RBT 2	(RBT 4)

Table 7: Allocation of RBTs

4

3.13 Excavation Classes (ECL)

Based on the determination of Geotechnical Units and Rock Mass Behaviour Types and the consideration of given constraints and requirements for the tunnelling operation the details of excavation procedures and support provisions, including auxiliary measures, are defined. Also, the performance of the composite system of tunnel support and rock surround is evaluated and compared with the requirements.

In order to create a manageable design and construction process a limited number of characteristic systems is identified, related to typical rock mass behaviour, excavation method and tunnel support. These are termed as Excavation Classes (ECL) and are the basis for the execution and contractual handling of the tunnel excavation works.

As a result of the geotechnical design six Excavation Classes have been developed. They differ in terms of round length, excavation sequence, required support, and auxiliary measures, but are all associated with conventional excavation methods (mostly Drill&Blast). A detailed description of the Excavation Classes will be given in the Design Report and the corresponding drawings, which also indicate the related quantities per lin.m of tunnel.

The particular Excavation Classes and their relationship to the Rock Mass Behaviour Types as defined in Chapter 3.11 are presented in the table below. In connection with the evaluation of the system behaviour for each Excavation Class the expected maximum deformations of the tunnel support have been derived, which are also included in this table.

Excavation Class	Related RBT	Max. Deformation [m]
1	RBT1	0,05
1a	RBT5	0,05
2	RBT2	0,05
3	RBT3	0,10
4	RBT4	0,15
5	RBT4	0,20

Table 8: Excavation Classes

3.14 Expected Excavation Class Distribution

From the anticipated allocation of Rock Mass Behaviour Types and the correlation between RBTs and Excavation Classes as shown above an expected distribution of Excavation Classes as percentage of the total tunnel length has been obtained. This takes into account the predominant, secondary or only minor occurrence of each RBT in the given sections.

The expected Excavation Class distribution, starting from the actual face of the existing tunnel at the South Portal is given in the table below. The length of the tunnel remaining for excavation is approximately 7923 m.

Excavation Class	[%]	[m]
1	17	1347
1a	4	317
2	54	4278
3	14	1109
4	6	475
5	5	396
Total	100	7923

Related Rock Mass
Behaviour Type
(RBT)

RBT 1
RBT 5
RBT 2
RBT 3
RBT 4
RBT 4

Table 9: Excavation Class Distribution

3.15 Geological Description of Platform Areas

The engineering geological units for platform areas are shown on the drawing "Geological Sections and Layout Map" of Lowari Rail Tunnel (Appendix A.1). The North Portal Platform is shown in more detail on the drawing "Alignment East and West - Geological Layout Map" of North Link Access Road (Appendix A.2).

3.15.1 Platform at South Portal

In the closer vicinity of the South Portal material already excavated from the tunnel is the base for the platform. It grades towards south into fluvial sediments of Mirga Khwar. Huge boulders with more than 2 m diameter can be found there. Further south sound granite and weathered biotite granite with a thick cover of slope debris form the underground for the platform. An open cut along the existing road was recently excavated by the use of mechanical equipment only, without the use of blasting. This indicates relative weak rock (biotite granite) near the surface.

3.15.2 Platform at North Portal

North of the North Portal Area fluvial sediments of Sharai Gol river with an estimated thickness of more than 10 m are prevailing. Seismic profiles in the surrounding river beds indicate a deep overburden of alluvium (up to 15 m) above the bedrock.

The platform area itself has a base of medium strong metavolcanic rock which is exposed at only a few spots. The main part of the platform is covered with slope debris which is grading into fluvial sediments. They can contain huge boulders with a diameter of more than 2 m. Secondary small creeks (nalas) which also provide a passage for mud flows and avalanches can be found in the north-western part of the platform.

3.16 Further Investigations

Additional subsurface investigations shall be performed when the exact location of large culverts or bridges, which are part of the tunnelling contract are fixed. A bridge or culvert will be built across Mirgha Khwar at the South Portal. Also, between Lowari Tunnel North Portal and Ziarat Post a bridge will be constructed. The exact location of bridge piers and abutments must be known before the start of additional ground investigation. Core drillings or trenches have to be performed to detect the location of the top of bedrock where it is covered by alluvium and/or slope debris.

3.17 Conclusion

Prediction of geological-geotechnical conditions of a tunnel with high overburden is generally difficult and contains a lot of uncertainties. Especially the exact prediction where rock borders and fault zones are located in the tunnel can only be an extrapolation from surface and comparatively shallow subsurface investigations. The results of the investigations lead to the following prediction for a drill and blast excavation:

- Excavation of Lowari Tunnel will be performed mostly in jointed, compact, but abrasive rock.
- Local water ingress up to 50 l/s is possible especially along minor fault zones. Some permanent minor water inflow will remain. If descending excavation drive is performed water has to be pumped out.
- In weaker rock portions a division of excavation into top heading, bench and invert will be necessary. Full face excavation is possible with additional long face bolting.
- Smaller portions of squeezing rock may be encountered
- Occurrence of rock burst cannot be excluded in high overburden areas.
- An enlargement of the standard cross section for by-passing of two trains will be situated approximately in the middle of the tunnel. In case of unfavourable rock mass conditions this location can be slightly shifted.

in part

4 NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD

4.1 Alignment and Topography

4.1.1 General

The alignment of the upper part of the existing Northern Access Road between Baradam and Ziarat Post is too steep to comply with the design criteria for the road improvement works. Therefore a new design of the North Link Access Road is required which shall provide the connection between the existing alignment of the Northern Access Road and the North Portal Facilities of the Lowari Tunnel, observing acceptable design standards.

4.1.2 Alignment West

A possible alignment of the North Link Access Road is situated west of Ashret Gol, starting at Ziarat Post. It will include two short tunnels, each with a length of approximately 200 m, several slope cuts, culverts and a large bridge crossing Ashret Gol at its lower end. The area west of Ashret Gol is generally very steep and the valley itself is very narrow. Only the side valley coming from Buzegan Gol is relatively wide with flatter inclination and is therefore proposed to provide the location for the descent of the new alignment towards the old road. The alignment is shown on the drawing "Alignment East and West – Geological Layout Map" (Appendix A.2). Photos of this road alignment can be seen in Appendix B.

4.1.3 Alignment East with Tunnel

The other possible alignment, on the east side of Ashret Gol (see Appendix A.2) will cross the river at km 1.1 with a 80 m long bridge and thereafter follow the right bank of the river. This alignment includes a 900 m long road tunnel section with a maximum overburden of approx. 240 m. The southern tunnel portal is reached at a short distance from the bridge in moderately difficult terrain. The tunnel features a slight curvature in plan and has a longitudinal gradient of 5%. Immediately after the north tunnel portal a slope bridge is proposed to cross a steep ravine. This location will also require measures for avalanche protection. Indications concerning other areas of potential avalanche risk are given on the drawing "Alignment East and West – Geological Layout Map" (Appendix A.2)

The road continues along the flank of the valley up to km 3.0 from where it doubles back to descend to the connection with the existing road at the edge of the river bed. Photos of this road alignment can be seen in Appendix B.

4.1.4 Alignment East without Tunnel (suggested for design):

A different new possible alignment option will follow the right bank of the Ashret Gol along the surface, without the provision of road tunnels. In the upper part this alignment will be identical to the solution of Chapter 4.1.3 (Alignment East with Tunnel). However, from the location of the north portal determined above the alignment will turn off and follow the valley slope along the surface, approximately 50 m to 90 m above the existing road. This potential alignment has so far been studied in a preliminary way, but not yet been designed in detail. Characteristic features are the crossing of steep rock walls and rock fall

areas in that section where it substitutes the road tunnel. In addition, avalanche paths which have not been considered for the tunnel section may present additional hazards for the surface road alignment or require protective structures. The preliminary solution proposed is shown on the drawing "Alignment East and West – Geological Layout Map" (Appendix A.2). Photos of this road alignment can be seen in Appendix B.

4.2 Existing Geological-Geotechnical Investigations

The existing geological geotechnical investigations cover the area of all proposed alignments. Engineering mapping units, orientation of discontinuities, rock mass types and rock behaviour types are therefore not discussed in separate chapters. The layout of the Alignment East Tunnel is parallel to the northern tunnel of the Alignment West and therefore the former is not indicated separately in the diagrams referring to the structural analysis of discontinuities.

4.2.1 Engineering Geological Mapping

Engineering geological mapping has been carried out during both studies performed in the year 2003 by Geoconsult –Typsa JV. Some results of this work prepared for the proposed Alignments West and East have already been presented in a Feasibility Study for the North Link Access Road [6]. The engineering-geological layout map of the area and the geological-geotechnical profiles for two short tunnels proposed for the Alignment West and the longer tunnel for the Alignment East are shown in Appendices A.2, A.3 and A.4.

Because of relatively low overburden and continuous outcrops in the vicinity of the tunnel alignment the prediction of rock conditions of the Alignment West will be comparatively precise.

4.3 Geological Overview

The North Link Access Road area has the same geological setting as Lowari Tunnel (see Chapter 3.3.) However, as a general feature, the schistosity here is much more distinctly developed than in the southern parts of the Lowari Tunnel project. Also, Metasediments have more favourable rock mass properties since Paragneiss and Quartzite are prevailing and Schists are found only rarely. Metasediments are not expected to be found in the road tunnels of Alignment West of the North Link Access Road. The possibility of the occurrence of earth quakes is comparable to Lowari Tunnel.

4.4 Engineering Geological Mapping Units

4.4.1 Slope Debris

The occurrence of slope debris varies considerably. Sound rock in the area of the North Link Access Road is usually covered only by a very thin layer or even shows no slope debris at all. Thicker layers of several meters of slope debris are found at Ziarat Post Platform and at locations 450 m and 650 m north of Ziarat Post on slopes east of Ashret Gol. Boulders in slope debris can reach a size of up to 3 m in diameter. Areas covered

completely by slope debris are shown on the drawing "Alignment East and West – Geological Layout Map" (Appendix A.2).

4.4.2 Fluvatile Sediments

Fluvatile sediments in beds of bigger rivers like Ashret Gol can reach a thickness of 15 m (according to SWECO Seismic investigation) above bedrock. These sediments result from erosion and are, in addition, originating from rock fall or debris flow from steep slopes. They consist mainly of coarse gravel, cobbles and boulders. Boulders up to a size of approximately 3 m diameter can be found in river beds. The lower part of Buzegan Gol is also thickly covered by fluvatile sediments. Fluvatile areas, as mapped, are shown in yellow colour on the drawing "Alignment East and West – Geological Layout Map" (Appendix A.2).

4.4.3 Metasediment Unit

This unit contains Quartzite, Paragneiss and Schists. Metasediments show different degrees of weathering on the surface. Quartzite and Paragneiss are only slightly weathered and form steep slopes or even rock walls. Schists (very seldom exposed north of Ziarat Post) show more intensive weathering. Compact rock is prevailing in this unit north of Ziarat Post. Metasediments are not expected to be found in the road tunnels of Alignment West of the North Link Access Road.

Rock types:	Quartzite, Paragneiss, Schists (rare)
Texture:	distinct schistosity banding in Quartzite visible
Expected quartz content:	Quartzite (>95%) Paragneiss (20 - 50%) Schists (<20%)
Spacing of discontinuities:	very close (2 cm – 6 cm) to close (6 cm – 20 cm; Schists) close (6 cm - 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm – 60 cm; Quartzite, Paragneiss)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium to high (schistosity)
Roughness of discontinuities:	medium
Surface of discontinuities:	stained and weathered, in parts fillings with mica visible
Weathering:	moderate to highly weathered on surface outcrops
Sensitivity to water:	high sensitivity of Schists indicated
UCS of rock sample:	5 - 20 MPa (Schists) 100 -> 200 MPa (Quartzite, Paragneiss)

Above information is given for the average rock mass. The Schists of the Metasediment Unit are supposed to be the weakest rock of those encountered in the project area. The presence of water will further reduce the shear strength properties of Schists.

4.4.4 Metavolcanic Unit

Metavolcanic rock is mostly exposed on the surface without signs of intensive weathering and forms steep slopes or even rock walls. Joints are usually stained and sometimes open due to expansion on slopes. Sound rock is prevailing.

Rock types:	Metavolcanic rock (banded volcanics, amphibolites)
Texture:	densely jointed slightly to distinct banding visible
Expected quartz content:	usually no quartz or <10%
Spacing of discontinuities:	close (6cm-20cm) to moderate (20cm-60cm)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	medium to high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	fresh to only slightly weathered
Sensitivity to water:	no sensitivity indicated
UCS of rock sample:	100 - >200 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass.

4.4.5 Metaigneous Unit

Metaigneous rock is mostly exposed on the surface without signs of intensive weathering. Joints are usually only stained and sometimes open due to expansion on slopes. Sound rock is prevailing and sheared portions are rare.

Rock types:	Metaigneous rock ("Ortho Gneiss")
Texture:	massive to jointed distinct gneissic banding visible
Expected quartz content:	>20% up to 50%
Spacing of discontinuities:	moderate (20cm-60cm) to wide (60cm-2m)
Persistence of discontinuities:	medium
Roughness of discontinuities:	high
Surface of discontinuities:	clean with some staining only, usually no infillings
Weathering:	fresh to only slightly weathered
Sensitivity to water:	no sensitivity indicated
UCS of rock sample:	100 - >200 MPa

Above information is given for the average rock mass. Due to local faulting and dense joint pattern weakening of rock mass may be encountered in short sections of rock cuts and tunnels.

4.5 Structural Analyses of Discontinuities

4.5.1 Schistosity

The area of the North Link Access Road is dominated by a NE-SW striking regime of schistosity. Most schistosity planes show that north-west dipping direction (see pole point diagram below), and the dip variation turns around a north-east – south-west orientated fold axis. This fold axis and foliation direction can be observed at many locations on site. The statistical center of gravity of schistosity pole points is 306/47 (Dipping towards WNW with 47°).

Figure 4-1: Schistosity for North Link Access Road Tunnels (center of gravity: 306/47): Summary of all measurements performed for tunnels at Alignment East and West. Orientation of tunnel axis of Alignment East is identical to northern tunnel of Alignment West.

4.5.2 Rock Joints and Slickensides

Rock joints show different main directions of strike. The most important joint set strikes WNW-ESE dipping both towards south and north.

Figure 4-2: Pole points and strike direction of joints: Summary of all measurements performed. Orientation of tunnel axis of Alignment East is identical to northern tunnel of Alignment West.

4.5.3 Faults

Faults show the following main directions:

- Faults parallel to the schistosity are exposed along the existing road, distinct in zones of relatively massive Orthogneiss.
- Faults parallel to the main joint set can be observed all over the project area.
- Sub-horizontal thrust planes are exposed on the existing road to Ziarat Post at an altitude of about 2100 to 2200 m.
- East-west striking faults can also be observed along the existing road. This fault system is relatively scarce.

Figure 4-3: Strike direction of faults: Summary of all measurements performed. Orientation of tunnel axis of Alignment East is identical to northern tunnel of Alignment West.

In the zones of proposed tunnels, both for Alignments East and West of the North Link Access Road, only few minor fault or shear zones have been found. Within the length of a tunnel itself only one minor fault is expected, which is located in the southern tunnel of the Alignment West (Appendix A.3).

4.6 Geotechnical Interpretation for Tunnels

The geotechnical interpretation for the road tunnels located within the North Link Access Road follows the same approach as applied for the Lowari Tunnel and explained in Chapter 3.8 above.

4.7 Geotechnical Units (GTU)

The subdivision of the road tunnels into Geotechnical Units has resulted in the following allocation:

Alignment West – Tunnel North: 2 Geotechnical Units

Alignment West – Tunnel South: 3 Geotechnical Units

Alignment East: 3 Geotechnical Units.

The distribution of Geotechnical Units along the tunnel alignments is shown in the drawings "Alignment West - Geological Sections Tunnel North & South" (Appendix A.3) and "Alignment East - Geological Sections of Tunnel" (Appendix A.4).

4.8 Rock Mass Types (RMT)

The following Rock Mass Types (RMT) can be found in the project area of the North Link Access Road. However, not all RMTs are expected to be encountered in the three tunnels of the selected alignment options.

Rock Mass Type	Rock type	Estimated Uniaxial Compressive Strength [MPa]		Weathering	Spacing of discontinuities [according ISRM]	Properties of discontinuities
		rock sample	rock mass			
RMT 3	Orthogneiss, occ. intercalations of amphibolite (Metaigenous unit)	>100-250	20 - 50	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	Clean, rough
RMT 4		>100-200	15 -45	Slightly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	Stained, rough
RMT 5	Metavolcanics	>100-200	15 - 50	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	Clean, rough
RMT 6		>50-200	10 - 35	Slightly weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm) to moderate (20 cm - 60 cm)	Stained, rough
RMT 7	Metasediments, mainly quartzite and paragneiss	>100-250	15 - 45	Fresh to slightly weathered	Moderate (20 cm – 60 cm) to wide (60 cm – 2m)	smooth
RMT 8	Metasediments, Mainly schists	5-25	1 - 5	Slightly to moderately weathered	Close (6 cm – 20 cm), occasionally very close (2 cm - 6 cm)	Smooth, fillings parallel schistosity
RMT 11	Fault and shear zones, crushed rock of any origin	1-5	0,5	Moderately to highly weathered	Sheared and crushed	

Table 10: Rock Mass Types

Estimation of rock mass strength was carried out according to Marinos & Hoek [16]. Input parameters are GSI (geological strength index), m_i (Hoek Brown constant varying for different rock types) and estimated UCS (field estimations also in [16]). By variation of GSI and UCS the range of expected rock mass strength was determined for each RMT. For results see Table 5: Rock Mass Parameters in Chapter 3.10.

Metamorphic Rock Mass with distinct schistosity shows anisotropic rock mass strength. Highest Rock Mass Strength is achieved perpendicular to schistosity. Weakest Rock Mass strength is given when the strike is parallel to an exposed rock surface and the major principal stress is orientated at approximately 30° ($45 - \phi/2$) to the plane of schistosity.

4.9 Rock Mass Behaviour Types (RBT)

A general indication of tunnelling conditions is given by means of Rock Mass Behaviour Types. The estimated distribution of RBTs is shown on the drawings "Alignment West - Geological Sections Tunnel North & South" (Appendix A.3) and "Alignment East - Geological Sections of Tunnel" (Appendix A.4). Predominant RBTs are shown in bold letters, secondary RBTs in normal letters and RBTs of minor occurrence are shown in brackets.

Rock Mass Behaviour also depends on the cross section of excavation. The cross section for North Link Access Road tunnels (approx. 65 m^2) is larger than the standard cross section (approx. 45 m^2) of Lowari Rail Tunnel.

The following RBTs, defined according to Austrian Guideline for Geomechanical Design [17], are applicable to North Link Access Road Tunnels:

Rock Mass Behaviour Type (RBT)	Description of potential failure modes/mechanisms during excavation of the unsupported rock mass
RBT 1 Stable	Stable rock mass with the potential of small local gravity induced falling or sliding of blocks
RBT 2 Stable with the potential of discontinuity controlled block fall	Deep reaching, discontinuity controlled, gravity induced falling and sliding of blocks, occasional local shear failure
RBT 3 Shallow spalling and shear failure mechanism, ravelling material from the crown	Shallow stress induced shear failures in combination with discontinuity and gravity controlled failure of the rock mass.

Table 11: Rock Mass Behaviour Types

The expected project specific rock mass behaviour is described for drill and blast excavation, assuming smooth blasting by skilled workers. Rock mass behaviour and common support possibilities are described below:

4.9.1 RBT1

Stable (intact) rock mass is characterized by the potential of small local gravity induced falling or sliding of blocks. After performing of scaling rock mass remains more or less stable. In the long term smaller portions can fall, if not supported, but overall stability will not be affected. Joint pattern is usually medium to wide and closed joints with rough

surface prevail. Very small displacements of tunnel profile can be expected, which subside soon after blasting. Presence of water has no effect on stability of rock mass.

- Spot bolting and shotcrete will be required occasionally during construction. Shotcrete and wire mesh will be required for long term protection of crown in case of close and unfavourable joint pattern.
- Type of excavation: Full face excavation.
Possible round lengths > 3 m.

4.9.2 RBT2

Small rock portions may fall or slide quite soon after blasting induced by discontinuities and gravity. Small displacements usually subside quickly. Joints are developed. Presence of water has some influence on rock mass stability.

- Bolting, shotcrete with wire mesh required.
- Type of excavation: Full face excavation,
Possible round lengths 2 to 3 m.

4.9.3 RBT3

Small to medium large rock portions may fall induced by discontinuities, gravity and occasional local shear failures. Shear failure propagation and development of shallow plastic zones. Displacements continue for some weeks but show a significant decrease of displacement rate after short time. Joints are well developed. Presence of water has negative effect on rock mass stability.

- Steel ribs (or better lattice girders), systematic bolting and shotcrete with wire mesh are required. Occasionally forepoling will be necessary.
- Type of excavation: Full face excavation with occasional face bolting and sealing of face with shotcrete,
Possible round lengths 1,4 to 2 m.

4.10 Predicted Allocation of Rock Mass Behaviour Types (RBT)

4.10.1 Alignment West

The predicted allocation of RBTs for the Tunnel North is shown in the table below:

Geotechnical Unit	Predominant	Minor
GTU 1	RBT 2	
GTU 2	RBT 1	(RBT 2)

Table 12: Allocation of RBTs - Alignment West - Tunnel North

The predicted allocation of RBTs for the Tunnel South is shown in the table below:

Geotechnical Unit	Predominant	Minor
GTU 1	RBT 2	(RBT 1, RBT 3)
GTU 2	RBT 1	(RBT 2)
GTU 3	RBT 2	(RBT 1)

Table 13: Allocation of RBTs - Alignment West - Tunnel South

4.10.2 Alignment East

The predicted allocation of RBTs for the tunnel is shown in the table below:

Geotechnical Unit	Predominant	Minor
GTU 1	RBT 2	(RBT 1, RBT 3)
GTU 2	RBT 2	(RBT 1, RBT 3)
GTU 3	RBT 2	(RBT 1)

Table 14: Allocation of RBTs: Alignment East

4.11 Excavation Classes

As a result of the geotechnical design three Excavation Classes have been developed for the tunnels of the North Link Access Road. They differ in terms of round length, excavation sequence, required support, and auxiliary measures, but are all associated with conventional excavation methods (mostly Drill&Blast). A detailed description of the Excavation Classes will be given in the Design Report and the corresponding drawings, which also indicate the related quantities per lin.m of tunnel.

The particular Excavation Classes and their relationship to the Rock Mass Behaviour Types as defined in Chapter 4.9 are presented in the table below. In addition, from the evaluation of the system behaviour for each Excavation Class the expected maximum deformations of the tunnel support have been derived, which are also included in this table.

Excavation Class	Related RBT	Max. Deformation [m]
I	RBT1	0,05
II	RBT2	0,10
III	RBT3	0,15

Table 15: Excavation Classes

4.12 Expected Excavation Class Distribution

From the anticipated allocation of Rock Mass Behaviour Types and the correlation between RBTs and Excavation Classes as shown above an expected distribution of Excavation Classes as percentage of the total tunnel length has been obtained. This takes into account the predominant, secondary or only minor occurrence of each RBT in the given sections.

The expected Excavation Class distribution for each of the road tunnels within the alignment options defined are given in the tables below.

4.12.1 Alignment West

Tunnel North:

Excavation class	[%]	[m]
I	55	140
II	45	110
Total	100	250

Table 16: Excavation Class Distribution - Tunnel North - Alignment West

Tunnel South:

Excavation class	[%]	[m]
I	55	90
II	40	70
III	5	10
Total	100	170

Table 17: Excavation Class Distribution - Tunnel South - Alignment West

4.12.2 Alignment East

Excavation class	[%]	[m]
I	40	360
II	50	450
III	10	90
Total	100	900

Table 18: Excavation Class Distribution - Alignment East

4.13 Geotechnical Interpretation for Road Sections

4.13.1 Alignment West

Rock Mass Types:

Between Ziarat Post and Tunnel North slope debris and fluvial sediments prevail. Only at approx. km 1.0 and near the North Portal area of Tunnel North sound compact metavolcanic rock is exposed. Between Tunnel North and Tunnel South and further towards Buzegan Gol the entire alignment up to approximately km 3.1 is situated in metaigneous compact rock. This rock has only occasionally a shallow slope debris overburden and shows only slight weathering. Joints of this rock are usually closed. In the wide river bed of Buzegan Gol (approx. between km 3.1 to km 4.1) fluvial sediments with large boulders prevail. From approx. km 4.1 to km 4.2 the road is situated in metasediments and partly in fluvial sediments. The abutments of the proposed bridge crossing Ashret Gol are situated in fluvial sediments.

Geological Structures:

The orientation of bedding planes is dipping medium steep towards NW. No major faults have been found. One smaller fault is situated near the North Portal of Tunnel North with a striking direction WNW – ESE. Joint orientation may cause some sliding wedges where cut slopes are parallel to WNW – ESE direction.

Geological Hazards:

Potential avalanche paths have to be crossed. They are situated near km 1.7, km 2.0, and km 2.3 and are shown with blue arrows on the drawing "Alignment East and West - Geological Layout Map" of North Link Access Road (Appendix A.2). Rock fall is also possible in many areas but is not affecting the existing road.

4.13.2 Alignment East with Tunnel

Rock Mass Types:

From Ziarat Post platform towards the bridge across Ashret Gol the road follows the same alignment as described above. Slope debris and fluvial sediments are prevailing. The location of the southern bridge abutment is covered with fluvial sediments. The northern abutment is situated partly in metavolcanic rock with small local faults. From there an approx. 150 m long stretch is covered with a thick layer of slope debris overlaying volcanic rock. After that metaigneous rock with minor slope debris overburden is prevailing before, south of the tunnel portal, again slope debris will be found. The immediate surrounding of the South Portal of the tunnel is consisting of sound metavolcanics. The North Portal area is situated in compact metasediments (mainly quartzite) with slope debris overburden. From the North Portal area onward the road construction will be performed in sound metasediments and metaigneous rock. Smaller faults will cross the alignment. The section from approx. km 3.94 to the existing road will be situated in blocky slope debris.

Geological Structures:

The main dip direction of banded volcanics, meta igneous rocks and metasediments is between 290° and 320° towards north-west, dipping with 35° to 75°. Small fault zones in

granitic meta igneous rocks show similar directions (320/45, 300/45, 306/40). A second, important fault direction strikes NNE-SSW, falling steep both to the west and to the east (028/72, 205/87). Subhorizontal thrust faults show a third main direction.

Geological Hazards:

Potential avalanche paths have to be crossed. They are situated at approx. km 1.5, km 2.45 and km 2.8 and are shown with blue arrows on the drawing "Alignment East and West - Geological Layout Map" of North Link Access Road (Appendix A.2). Rock fall is also very common in this area. During construction of the new road sections north and south of the proposed tunnel the existing road may locally be exposed to major rock fall due to excavation carried out above.

4.13.3 Alignment East without Tunnel (not yet designed)

No tunnel will be constructed for this alignment. Therefore no Rock Mass Behaviour Types are given and only the expected rock mass types are described.

Rock Mass Types:

From approx km 1.55 to km 1.85 banded metavolcanic rocks with intercalations of meta igneous rocks prevail. Km 1.85 to km 2.6 is dominated by metaigneous rocks with mainly orthogneiss of granite and granodiorite. Km 2.6 to km 3.0 is situated in metasediments. After a thin intercalation of schists (some meters) paragneiss and quartzite are prevailing. From km 3.0 to km 3.15 again metaigneous rock is prevailing. Between km 3.15 to km 3.5 metasediments and between km 3.5 to km 3.55 metaigneous rocks are dominating. Thereafter the road is located in slope debris.

Geological Structures:

The identified structures are identical to the alignment with tunnel. The main dip direction of banded volcanics, meta igneous rocks and metasediments is between 290° and 320° towards north-west, dipping with 35° to 75°. Small fault zones in granitic meta igneous rocks show similar directions (320/45, 300/45, 306/40). A second, important fault direction strikes NNE-SSW, falling steep both to the west and to the east (028/72, 205/87). Subhorizontal thrust faults show a third main direction.

Geological Hazards:

Avalanche paths are located at km 1.5 and km 2.9 and are shown with blue arrows on the drawing "Alignment East and West - Geological Layout Map" of North Link Access Road (Appendix A.2). There are about one dozen of small creeks to be crossed by the road alignment. Only three of them are permanently flowing with water.

The rock fall risk for the new road will be as high as for the existing road. In addition, construction of the new road may cause major rock fall on parts of the existing road. Therefore, road construction will require the closure of the existing road for a considerable period of time.

4.14 Further Investigations

Additional subsurface investigations shall be performed when the exact location of large culverts or bridges, which are part of the North Link Access Road works are fixed. For each of the alignment options a Bridge will be constructed across Ashret Gol. The exact location of piers and abutments must be known before the start of additional ground investigations. Core drillings or trenches have to be performed to detect the location of the top of bedrock where it is thickly covered by alluvium and/or slope debris.

4.15 Conclusion

The geotechnical interpretation of the North Link Access Road project area can be summarized as follows:

- Rock Masses in the North Link Access Road area are expected to be mainly sound and compact. Only minor faults have been detected in the surroundings of the alignment options investigated.
- Slope debris with relevant thickness and/or fluvial sediments are only expected at Ziarat Post and along the lower parts of Buzegan Gol and Ashret Gol.
- Due to widespread rock exposure and comparatively low overburden above the road tunnels a good prediction quality can be obtained for both the Alignments West and East.
- Only small quantities of water are expected in the tunnels of the Alignment West except during snow melting and rainy season. Tunnel excavation for the two tunnels of the Alignment West can be performed also in descending direction, due to short tunnel lengths.
- Larger temporary inflow out of faults (up to 50 l/s), decreasing to a smaller permanent inflow is expected for the tunnel of the Alignment East. Descending excavation may have disadvantages in this instance because water has to be pumped out.

Salzburg, 06-05-2004

Dr. J. Golser

Julio Grande Florez

Appendix A: Drawings

- Appendix A.1: Lowari Rail Tunnel – Geological Sections and Layout Map (Drg. No. LTP.B1.TD.GG.GC.LA_003)
- Appendix A.2: North Link Access Road – Alignment West and East – Geological Layout Map (Drg. No. LTP.B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_001)
- Appendix A.3: North Link Access Road – Alignment West – Tunnel North and South – Geological Sections (Drg. No. TP.B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_002)
- Appendix A.4: North Link Access Road – Alignment East – Tunnel East – Geological Sections (Drg. No. LTP.B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_003)

CHAINAGE IN km.	8.000	7.000	6.000	5.000	4.000	3.000	2.000	1.000	0.00				
ALREADY EXCAVATED													
ENGINEERING GEOLOGICAL UNITS	ORTHOGNEISS WITH INTERCALATIONS OF AMPHIBOLITE			METASEDIMENTS, ORTHOGNEISS WITH INTERCALATIONS OF AMPHIBOLITE		ORTHOGNEISS WITH INTERCALATIONS OF AMPHIBOLITE		GRANITE TO GRANODIORITE		BIOTITE GRANITE AND GRANITE	GRANITE TO GRANODIORITE LOCAL WITH SMALL AMPHIBOLITE SILLS	BIOTITE GRANITE AND GRANITE	GRANITIC ROCK DOMINATING WITH GABBRO INTERSECTION
ROCK MASS TYPE	RMT8 (RMT7), RMT3 (RMT4), RMT8 (RMT7), RMT8 (RMT11)			RMT3 (RMT4), RMT3 (RMT11)		RMT1 (RMT2), RMT2 (RMT11)		RMT1 (RMT2), RMT2 (RMT11)		RMT9 (RMT10), RMT10 (RMT11)	RMT1 (RMT2), RMT2 (RMT11)	RMT1 (RMT2), RMT2 (RMT11)	
GEO TECHNICAL UNIT	GTU8, GTU7, GTU8			GTU3		GTU5, GTU4		GTU3		GTU1	GTU2	GTU1	
ROCK MASS BEHAVIOUR TYPE	RBT3 (RBT4), RBT1 (RBT3), RBT3 (RBT4)			RBT2 (RBT1), RBT1 (RBT4)		RBT2 (RBT5), RBT5 (RBT1), RBT1 (RBT4)		RBT3 (RBT2), RBT2 (RBT4)		RBT1 (RBT2), RBT2 (RBT3)	RBT2 (RBT3), RBT3 (RBT4)	RBT1 (RBT2), RBT2 (RBT3)	
GEO TECHNICAL REMARKS	INTENSIVELY JOINTED ROCK PREVAILING; WEAK ROCK IN METASEDIMENTS; LOCAL DANGER OF BIGGER OVERBREAKS.			OCC. SMALL OVERBREAKS, GENERAL SOUND ROCK WITH ONLY STAINED JOINTS; PORTION OF INTENSIVELY JOINTED ROCKS NEAR FAULTS (SMALL)		ΔH>900m POSSIBILITY OF ROCK BURST		LOCAL DANGER OF BIGGER OVERBREAKS		OCC. SMALL OVERBREAKS, GENERAL SOUND ROCK WITH ONLY STAINED JOINTS; PORTION OF INTENSIVELY JOINTED ROCKS NEAR FAULTS (SMALL)			
EXPECTED WATER INFLOW	LOCAL SHORT TIME INFLOW 20l/s; PERMANENT INFLOW <5l/s			LOCAL SHORT TIME INFLOW 40l/s; PERMANENT INFLOW <5l/s		LOCAL SHORT TIME INFLOW 50l/s; PERMANENT INFLOW <10l/s		LOCAL SHORT TIME INFLOW 40l/s; PERMANENT INFLOW <5l/s		LOCAL SHORT TIME INFLOW 20l/s; PERMANENT INFLOW <5l/s			

LEGEND:

- GRANITE UNIT
- INTERCALATION OF GABBRO
- METASEDIMENT UNIT
- METAVOLCANIC UNIT
- META IGNEOUS UNIT
- BIOTITE GRANITE UNIT
- FLUVIAL DEPOSIT SLOPE DEBRIS
- ALREADY EXCAVATED TOP HEADING/BENCH
- FRACTURE ZONE
- ESTIMATED FAULT

LONGITUDINAL SECTION
SCALE 1:20000

SECTION H-H'
SCALE 1:20000

SECTION I-I'
SCALE 1:20000

SECTION J-J'
SCALE 1:20000

PLAN VIEW
SCALE 1:20000

CLIENT ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY ISLAMABAD	JOINT VENTURE 	IN ASSOCIATION WITH 	E					DATE	NAME	PROJECT TITLE LOWARI RAIL TUNNEL PROJECT			
			D					ORIGINATED	03/04		GC		
			C					DESIGNED	03/04	GHo			
			B					DRAWN	03/04	IHa			
			A	18-03-04	DRAFT ISSUE	IHa	GSu	KLa	CHECKED	15-03-04	GSu		
			REV.	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DRAWN	CHECKED	APPROVED	APPROVED	18-03-04	KLa		
										DOC. NUMBER	LTP.B1.TD.GG.GC.LA_003	REV.	A1
										CAD FILE	LTP-B1-TD-GG-GC-LA_003	SCALE:	1:20000

CHAINAGE IN m.	1+925	1+905	1+885	1+865	1+845	1+825	1+805	1+785	1+765	1+745	1+725	1+705	1+685
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ENGINEERING GEOLOGICAL UNITS	META IGNEOUS UNIT: MASSIVE ORTHOGEISS OF GRANITE AND GRANODIORITE, POSSIBLY INTERCALATIONS OF AMPHIBOLITE		
ROCK MASS TYPE	RMT3		RMT2
GEO TECHNICAL UNIT	GTU1		GTU2
ROCK MASS BEHAVIOUR TYPE	RBT2		RBT1 (RBT2)
GEO TECHNICAL REMARKS			SOUND ROCK PREVAILING ONLY SMALLER OVERBREAKS EXPECTED
EXPECTED WATER INFLOW	SMALL INFLOW FROM SURFACE		MINOR WATER INFLOW OF SUBSURFACE WATER

LONGITUDINAL SECTION A-A'
SCALE 1:1000

CROSS SECTION D-D'
SCALE 1:1000

CROSS SECTION E-E'
SCALE 1:1000

CHAINAGE IN km.	1+500	1+480	1+460	1+440	1+420	1+400	1+380	1+360	1+340
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ENGINEERING GEOLOGICAL UNITS	META IGNEOUS UNIT: MASSIVE ORTHOGEISS OF GRANITE AND GRANODIORITE POSSIBLY INTERCALATIONS OF AMPHIBOLITE	BANDED META-VOLCANICS, AMPHIBO.	
ROCK MASS TYPE	RMT3, RMT4, (RMT11)		RMT8, RMT6
GEO TECHNICAL UNIT	GTU1	GTU2	GTU3
ROCK MASS BEHAVIOUR TYPE	RBT2, RBT1, (RBT3)	RBT1, (RBT2)	RBT2, RBT1
GEO TECHNICAL REMARKS	FAULT WITH MINOR INFLUENCE		
EXPECTED WATER INFLOW	SMALL WATER INFLOW FROM SURFACE POSSIBLE	IN JOINTED AREAS AND PARALLEL BEDDING MINOR WATER INFLOW	

LONGITUDINAL SECTION B-B'
SCALE 1:1000

LEGEND:

- SLOPE DEBRIS
- RECENT FLUVIAL DEPOSIT
- METAVOLCANIC UNIT
- META IGNEOUS UNIT
- FAULT (ESTIMATED)

PLAN VIEW
SCALE 1:10000

CLIENT
**ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN
NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY
ISLAMABAD**

JOINT VENTURE
GC GEOCONSULT
TYPSA
INGENIEROS CONSULTORES Y ARQUITECTOS

IN ASSOCIATION WITH
Loya associates

E								DATE	NAME
D								ORIGINATED	12/03
C								DESIGNED	12/03
B								DRAWN	02/04
A	18-03-04	DRAFT ISSUE						CHECKED	15-03-04
REV.	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DRAWN	CHECKED	APPROVED	APPROVED	APPROVED	18-03-04	KL

PROJECT TITLE LOWARI RAIL TUNNEL PROJECT		
DRAWING TITLE NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD ALIGNMENT WEST GEOLOGICAL SECTIONS TUNNEL NORTH & SOUTH		
DOC. NUMBER	LTP-B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_002	REV. A1
CAD FILE	LTP-B4-FS-GG-GC-LA_002	SCALE:1:1000, 1:10000

CLIENT

**ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN
NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY
ISLAMABAD**

JOINT VENTURE

IN ASSOCIATION WITH

E		
D		
C		
B		
A	18-03-04	DRAFT ISSUE
REV.	DATE	DESCRIPTION

- LEGEND:**
- CULTIVATED AREA
 - SLOPE DEBRIS
 - RECENT FLUVIAL DEPOSIT
 - METASEDIMENT UNIT
 - METAVOLCANIC UNIT
 - METAIGNEOUS UNIT
 - ESTIMATED FAULT
 - DIP DIRECTION
 - POSSIBLE AVALANCHE STRIP

JOINT VENTURE		IN ASSOCIATION WITH						PROJECT TITLE		
								LOWARI RAIL TUNNEL PROJECT		
								DRAWING TITLE		
								NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD ALIGNMENT EAST AND WEST GEOLOGICAL LAYOUT MAP		
REV.	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DRAWN	CHECKED	APPROVED	APPROVED	DATE	NAME	DOC. NUMBER	REV.
A	18-03-04	DRAFT ISSUE	IHa	GSu	KLd	CHECKED	15-03-04	GSu	LTP-B4-FS-GG-GC-LA_001	A1
							18-03-04	KLd	LTP-B4-FS-GG-GC-LA_001.dwg	SCALE: 1:5000

LEGEND:

- METASEDIMENT UNIT
- METAVOLCANIC UNIT
- META IGNEOUS UNIT
- FLUVIAL DEPOSIT
SLOPE DEBRIS
- SLOPE DEBRIS
- ESTIMATED FAULT

CHAINAGE IN km.	2+400	2+300	2+200	2+100	2+000	1+900	1+800	1+700	1+600	1+500	
ENGINEERING GEOLOGICAL UNITS	META SEDIMENT QUARZITE; SLOPE DEBRIS WILL BE REMOVED		META IGNEOUS UNIT: MASSIVE ORTHOGNEISS OF GRANITE AND BANDED META GRANODIORITE					BANDED META-VOLCANICS, AMPHIBOLITE			
ROCK MASS TYPE	RMT7 (RMT 11)		RMT4 RMT3 (RMT 11)					RMT6 RMT7 (RMT 11)			
GEOTECHNICAL UNIT	GTU1		GTU2					GTU3			
ROCK MASS BEHAVIOUR TYPE	(RBT1) (RBT2) (RBT3)		RBT2 (RBT 3)					RBT2 RBT1			
GEOTECHNICAL REMARKS	FAULT AT LOW ANGLE TO TUNNEL AXIS		FAULT AT LOW ANGLE TO TUNNEL AXIS					FAULT AT LOW ANGLE TO TUNNEL AXIS			
EXPECTED WATER INFLOW	SMALL INFLOW FROM SURFACE ESPACIALLY DURING SNOW MELT OR IN RAINY SEASON		TEMPORARY INFLOW OUT OF FAULTS UP TO 50l/s PERMANENT INFLOW $\geq$ 10l/s					SMALL INFLOW FROM SURFACE ESPACIALLY DURING SNOW MELT OR AND IN RAINY SEASON			

LONGITUDINAL SECTION C-C'
SCALE 1:2000

PLAN VIEW
SCALE 1:10000

CROSS SECTION F-F'
SCALE 1:2000

CROSS SECTION G-G'
SCALE 1:2000

CLIENT ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY ISLAMABAD	JOINT VENTURE GC GEOCONSULT TYPSA INGENIEROS CONSULTORES Y ARQUITECTOS	IN ASSOCIATION WITH Loya associates	E					DATE	NAME	PROJECT TITLE					
			D					ORIGINATED	03/04	GC	LOWARI RAIL TUNNEL PROJECT				
			C					DESIGNED	03/04	GHo	DRAWING TITLE				
			B					DRAWN	03/04	IHa	NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD ALIGNMENT EAST GEOLOGICAL SECTIONS OF TUNNEL				
			A	18-03-04	DRAFT ISSUE	IHa	GSu	KLa	CHECKED	15-03-04	GSu	DOC. NUMBER	LTP.B4.FS.GG.GC.LA_003	REV.	A1
			REV.	DATE	DESCRIPTION	DRAWN	CHECKED	APPROVED	APPROVED	18-03-04	KLa	CAD FILE	LTP-B4-FS-GG-GC-LA_003.dwg	SCALE:	1:2000, 1:10000

Appendix B: Photo Documentation

1 LOWARI TUNNEL

1.1 South Portal

Fig. 1: Situation at south portal.

Fig. 2: The south portal.

Fig. 3: Recent situation at the south portal.

Fig. 4: Seepage water at south portal (appr. 1 l/s).

Fig. 5: Inside the existing tunnel (face, approximately station 593 m).

1.2 South Station

Fig. 6: Station situation, from the south portal to the south.

Fig. 7: Culvert or bridge situation at south portal (Mirga Khwar).

1.3 North Portal

Fig. 8: The north portal will be constructed right in the center of the picture. Left side: Trangar Gol, right side: Sharai Gol. Picture taken from Ziarat Post.

Fig. 9: Recent situation at north portal, Sharai Gol. Picture taken from mouth of Trangar Gol.

Fig. 10: Culvert or bridge situation at north portal (Sharai Gol). At the left: existing road to Lowari Pass.

Fig. 11: Exploratory adit no. 5 at north portal area.

1.4 North Station

Fig. 12: Ziarat Post (position of station).

Fig. 13: Position of descend from northern station. Picture taken from Gotus Gol.

Fig. 14: Position of descend from northern station. Picture taken from Ashret Gol.

2 NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD – WESTERN ALIGNMENT

2.1 Tunnel South

Fig. 15: Tunnel alignment and Ashret Gol.

Fig. 16: Position of south portal.

Fig. 17: South portal – detail.

Fig. 18: Position of north portal.

Fig. 19: Tunnel alignment:
NW-SE-striking faults.

Fig. 20: Tunnel alignment:
Metavolcanic unit.

Fig. 21: Tunnel alignment:
Metaigneous unit
(orthogneiss).

2.2 Tunnel North

Fig. 22: Alignment of Tunnel North.

Fig. 23: Position of south portal.

Fig. 24: Detail of south portal.

Fig. 25: Detail of north portal.

Fig. 26: Ashret Gol, beneath Tunnel North.

2.3 Descend to Existing Road (Buzegán Gol) and Ashret Gol Crossing

Fig. 27: Between north portal of Tunnel North and Buzegán Gol.

Fig. 28: Buzegán Gol: Overview.

Fig. 29: Buzegán Gol: Mouth into Ashret Gol.

Fig. 30: Ashret Gol: Left side – bridge foundation.

Fig. 31: Ashret Gol: Right side – bridge foundation.

3 NORTH LINK ACCESS ROAD – EASTERN ALIGNMENT – TUNNEL / SURFACE

3.1 South Portal

Fig. 32: Situation of South Portal of Eastern Alignment – Tunnel (red) and street cut of Eastern Alignment – Surface (blue).

Fig. 33: Detail at South Portal.

3.2 North Portal

Fig. 34: Situation of North Portal of Version East – Tunnel (red) and Situation of Version East – Surface (blue).

Fig. 35: Detail at North Portal.

**3.3 Alignment
(Version Tunnel +
Version Surface)**

Fig. 36: Cut situation at Km 1.2 to 1.4

Fig. 37: Version East – Surface.

Fig. 38: Version East – Situation at “Hotel” (Km 2.6 to 3.0).

Fig. 39: Version East – Descend to existing road near Baradam.

4 ROCK SAMPLES

Fig. 40: Rock sample 1:
Banded volcanics.
Sample taken from
Lowari Tunnel north
portal area.

Fig. 41: Detail of rock
sample 1, approximate
scale: 2:1.

Fig. 42: Rock sample 2:
Orthogneiss of
Granodiorite, taken at
current Lowari Pass
road.

Fig. 43: Detail of rock sample 2, approximate scale: 2:1.

Fig. 44: Rock sample 3: Orthogneiss of Granite, sample taken at North Link Access Road, tunnel north, south portal.

Fig. 45: Detail of rock sample 3, approximate scale: 2:1.

Fig. 46: Rock sample 4: Volcanic rock, sample taken at North Link Access Road, tunnel south, south portal.

Fig. 47: Detail of rock sample 4, approximate scale: 2:1.

Fig. 48: Rock sample 5: Granite, sample taken inside existing Lowari Tunnel.

Fig. 49: Detail of rock sample 5, approximate scale: 2:1.

Appendix C: Previous Investigations

Appendix C.1: Thin Sections: Petrographic Results

Appendix C.2: Drill Holes A, B, D, E

Appendix C.3: Drill Hole LTB 2

Appendix C.4: Drill Hole LTB 4

Appendix C.5: Drill Holes LT-1, LT-2, LT-3

Appendix C.6: Seismic Lines

Appendix C.7: Water Analyses

7042-D-4042

PETROGRAPHIC RESULTS

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
 Bore Hole No: LT-3
 Depth: 60'-60'-4"
 Slide No: 666

Feldspar

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Magascopeic Description:

Light-grey in colour, medium-grained and well compacted. Green coloured minerals are probably amphiboles.

Microscopic Description:

Medium to fine-grained, consisting of large angular grains of feldspar and irregular grains of amphiboles embedded in a matrix of fine grained matrix of feldspar, amphibole, epidote, pyroxene and zeolites etc. Feldspar grains are highly weathered into sericite and clay-mineral etc. Some open cracks have been developed, filled by some mineral probably serpentine. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate moderate compaction.

Approx: Mineral Composition:

Feldspar:	75%
Amphibole:	12%
Epidote:	5%
Zeolite:	3%
Pyroxene:	2%
Iron-ore:	2%
Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name:

Dolerite

Remarks:

No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

...

Project:	Lowari Pass Tunnel
Location:	L (As marked on geological map No.LTP-2)
Sample No:	25
Slide No:	667

Quartz

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Magascopic Description:	Dark-grey in colour, very fine grained, well compacted and stratified (not so well defined).
Microscopic Description:	Very fine grained, slightly banded and consisting of sub-rounded grains of quartz and a few grains of feldspar of varying sizes, embedded in a ground mass of some secondary material. Matrix shows the evidence of alteration, however texture suggests that the matrix was once glassy and now devitrified and recrystallized. Much of the secondary material in the matrix is of an epidotic, zoisitic and sericitic types. There is some indication of flow structure. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.
Petrographic Name:	Probably a devitrified acid lava of rhyolitic composition.
Remarks:	As the rock constitutes, mainly, altered and devitrified lava, so it is not suitable for concrete aggregate or any be reactive to ordinary cement.

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
 Location: M (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
 Sample No: Z-1
 Slide No: 668

Feldspar

Quartz

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Magasopic Description: Dark-grey in colour, fine to medium grained, well compacted and stratified (not so well defined).

Microscopic Description: Fine to medium grained, slightly banded and consisting of sub-angular to sub-rounded grains of feldspar and quartz of varying sizes, embedded in a ground-mass of some secondary material. Feldspar includes plagioclase and potash-feldspar. Matrix shows the evidence of alteration and texture indicates that matrix was once glassy and now devitrified and recrystallized. Secondary material in the matrix is of an epidotic, zircitic and sericitic type. There is a rough indication of flow structure. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.

Petrographic Name: Probably a devitrified acid lava of rhyolitic composition.

Remarks: As the rock constitutes, mainly, altered and devitrified lava, so it is not suitable for concrete aggregate or may be reactive to ordinary cement.

...

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
Location: N (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
Sample No: LZ-5
Slide No: 669

Feldspar

Quartz

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description: Greenish-grey in colour, medium-grained and well compacted. Dark green coloured minerals are probably amphiboles.

Microscopic Description: Medium, to coarse grained, slightly foliated texture and composed of sub-rounded to sub-angular grains of feldspar and quartz, Feldspar includes plagioclase and potash feldspar, which show the phenomenon of alteration into sericites and clay-minerals. Some larger feldspar grains have corroded outlines and coarse perthitic texture. Amphiboles are generally elongated in shape and mark the foliation planes. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.

Approx: Mineral	Feldspar:	55%
Composition:	Quartz:	37%
	Amphibole:	5%
	Iron-ore:	2%
	Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name: Quartzo-Feldspathic Hornfels.

Remarks: No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
Location: P (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
Sample No: LZ-7
Slide No: 670

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description: Greenish-grey in colour, medium grained and well compacted. Dark green coloured minerals are probably amphiboles.

Microscopic Description: Medium grained, very slightly foliated and consists of sub-rounded to sub-angular grains of feldspar and quartz. Feldspar includes plagioclase and potash feldspar and exhibits the phenomenon of coarse perthite texture. Amphiboles are irregular in shape and mark the foliation planes. Texture and orientation of minerals indicates well compaction.

Approx: Mineral	Feldspar:	55%
Composition:	Quartz:	37%
	Amphiboles:	5%
	Iron-ore:	2%
	Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name: Quartzo-feldspathic Hornfels.

Remarks: No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
 Location: D (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
 Sample No: 60
 Slide No: 671

Quartz

Feldspar

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description:

Dark-grey in colour, coarse-grained and well compacted. Gneissic structure is marked by parallel alignment of dark coloured minerals probably biotite.

Microscopic Description:

Coarse grained, consisting of sub-angular to sub-rounded grains of feldspar and quartz and lakes of biotite and amphibole. Feldspar includes mainly plagioclase and some orthoclase and microcline. Feldspar grains show the phenomenon of alteration into clay minerals and sericite. Biotite and amphibole flakes mark the gneissic planes. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate moderate compaction.

Approx: Mineral Composition:

Feldspar:	85%
Quartz:	8%
Biotite:	3%
Amphibole:	2%
Iron-ore	1%
Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name:

Granodioritic Gneiss.

Remarks:

No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

...

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
 Location: B (As marked on Geological Map No: LTP-2)
 Sample No: 14
 Slide No: 672

Amphibole

Feldspar

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description: Greenish grey in colour, coarse grained and well compacted. Dark green coloured minerals are probably amphiboles.

Microscopic Description: Coarse grained, consisting of mainly angular to sub-angular grains of feldspar and quartz and irregular grains of amphibole. Feldspar includes mainly plagioclase with some potash-feldspar. Some plagioclase grains show the phenomenon of alteration into sericite and clay-minerals. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.

Approx: Mineral	Feldspar:	79%
Composition:	Amphibole:	15%
	Quartz:	3%
	Iron-ore:	2%
	Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name: Diorite

Remarks: No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

...

Project:
Location:
Sample No:
Slide No:

Lowari Pass Tunnel
H (As marked on Geological Map No: LTP-2)
31
673

Quartz

Feldspar

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description:

Grey in colour, medium-grained and well compacted. Dark-green coloured minerals are probably amphiboles.

Microscopic Description:

Coarse grained, consisting of mainly sub-angular to sub-rounded grains of feldspar and quartz with some irregular grains of amphiboles. Feldspar includes potash-feldspar and plagioclase. Feldspar grains are slightly altered into sericite etc. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.

Approx: Mineral
Composition:

Feldspar:	65%
Quartz:	25%
Amphibole:	8%
Iron-ore:	1%
Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name:

Granite

Remarks:

No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

Project: Lowari Pass Tunnel
 Location: C (As marked on Geological Map No LTP-2)
 Sample No: 51
 Slide No: 674

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description: Dark-grey in colour, fine grained and well compacted. Dark coloured minerals are probably amphiboles and iron ore.

Microscopic Description: Medium grained, consisting of mainly angular to sub-angular grains of feldspar and quartz and irregular grains of amphibole and iron-ore. Feldspar includes plagioclase and potash feldspar. Mineralogy indicates that the sample is a part of some mixed rock (Migmatite) of acid and basic components. Texture and orientation of minerals indicates well compaction.

Approx: Mineral	Feldspar:	63%
Composition:	Amphibole:	18%
	Quartz:	10%
	Iron-ore:	8%
	Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name: Migmatite

Remarks: No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

...

Project:
Location:
Sample No:
Slide No:

Lowari Pass Tunnel
F (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
41
675

Quartz

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description:

Grey in colour, medium-grained and well compacted. Gneissic structure is marked by parallel alignment of dark coloured minerals probably biotite.

Microscopic Description:

Medium grained, consisting of mainly sub-angular to sub-rounded grains of feldspar and quartz and flakes of biotite with some muscovite and iron-ore. Feldspar includes potash-feldspar and plagioclase and shows the phenomenon of alteration into sericite and clay mineral. Biotite flakes mark the gneissic plane. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate well compaction.

Approx: Mineral Composition:

Feldspar:	59%
Quartz:	25%
Biotite:	10%
Muscovite:	2%
Clay Minerals:	2%
Iron-ore:	1%
Epidote:	1%

Petrographic Name:

Granitic Gneiss

Remarks:

No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

Project:
Location:
Sample No:
Slide No:

Lowari Pass Tunnel
R (As marked on Geological Map No.LTP-2)
LZ-9
680

Feldspar

Quartz

Photomicrograph of the slide x 114.

Megascopic Description:

Brownish-grey in colour, coarse grained and very loosely compacted. Dark coloured minerals are probably biotite.

Microscopic Description:

Coarse grained, slightly banded, consisting of sub-angular to irregular grains of feldspar and quartz with some biotite and iron-ore. Feldspar includes mainly potash-feldspar with some plagioclase. Feldspar and quartz grains are generally broken and intruded by cracks. These cracks are oriented in a parallel alignment filled by some secondary mineral. Texture and orientation of minerals indicate very loose compaction.

Approx: Mineral
Composition:

Feldspar:	69%
Quartz:	27%
Biotite:	2%
Iron-ore:	1%
Acc: Min.	1%

Petrographic Name:

Granite

Remarks:

No Alkaline Reactive mineral seem to be present which may adversely affect the concrete aggregate or the cement used for construction.

...

REMARKS

-2318

+2300

+2290

+2280

10

20

30

40

Volcanic rock black/green

Calcite veins Epidotrich

Coaltr

mostly Fe ca ->

ep

cl

cl

ss

cl

cl

cl

cl

cl

ep

ep

More than 20 fractures per m

>15 15

Above 20 5 15

Above 20

More than 20 fractures per m

10

20

30

40

LEGENDS

WEATHERING
 W1 = FRESH ROCK
 W2 = WEATHERED
 W3 = HIGHLY WEATHERED

JOINT FILLING, COMPOSITION
 Ca = CALCITE
 Cl = CLORITE
 Fe = IRON
 Ep = EPOXY
 Qz = QUARTZ
 SS = SLICKENSIDE

MOSTLY CL - MOST FREQUENT
 JOINT FILLING MINERAL

ROD
 100 - 90 % EXCELLENT
 90 - 75 % GOOD
 75 - 50 % FAIR
 50 - 25 % POOR
 25 - 0 % VERY POOR

GROUND LEVEL: +2319.32 m.

DRILLHOLE LOCATION
 X=3087009.05
 Y=1239935.03
 Z=+2319.32

REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN		ISLAMABAD
NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY		
S&E	STC0004LM	LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
AND		DRILL HOLE &
PACIFIC CONSULTANTS		CORE LOG
INTERNATIONAL	TOKYO	
95323		04

LEGENDS

WEATHERING
 W₁ = FRESH ROCK
 W₂ = WEATHERED
 W₃ = HIGHLY WEATHERED

JOINT FILLING, DOMINATING
 Ca = CALCITE
 Cl = CLORITE
 Fe = IRON
 Ep = EPODOT
 Oz = QUARTZ
 Ss = SLICKENSIDE

MOSTLY Cl → MOST FREQUENT
 JOINT FILLING MINERAL

ROD
 100 - 90 % EXCELLENT
 90 - 75 % GOOD
 75 - 50 % FAIR
 50 - 25 % POOR
 25 - 0 % VERY POOR

GROUND LEVEL: +2329.12 m

DRILLHOLE LOCATION
 X=3087029.73
 Y=1239914.32
 Z=+2329.12

REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN	
NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY . SLAMABAD	
SWE O . STOCKHOLM	LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
AND	DRILL HOLE S
PACIFIC CONSULTANTS	CORE LOG
INTERNATIONAL	TKYO
95323	G 15

Level amsl (m)

+2310

+2300

2290

Drilllength (m)
Core run
Oriented core(ko)

Core recovery (%)

Rocktype

Volcanic rock black/dark green fine grained
 Granodioritic type grey-dark grey medium grained
 homogenous-slightly banded quartz veins
 Volcanic rock black/dark green
 Granodioritic type grey

Weathering(1-3)3
W2
W1

Aver. dip of joints acc. to core axis

Joint roughness

Joint filling

Fractures per m

RQD

Drilllength (m)

REMARKS

2290

+2280

+2270

+2260

30

30

40

50

ins
 bl
 picritic rock
 blk/dark green Granodioritic type grey-dark grey medium grained nonagenius-slightly banded quartz veins

ct

w

cl

cl

cl

ep

qz mostly ca->

ep

qz

ep

cl

fe

ep

ss

ss

cl

20 20 20

30

40

50

60

LEGENDS

WEATHERING
 W₁ = FRESH ROCK
 W₂ = WEATHERED
 W₃ = HIGHLY WEATHERED

JOINT FILLING DOMINATING
 Co = CALCITE
 Cl = CLORITE
 Fe = IRON
 Ep = EPIDOT
 Jz = QUARTZ
 Ss = SLICKENSIDE

MOSTLY CL → MOST FREQUENT
 JOINT FILLING MINERAL

ROQ
 100 - 90 % EXCELLENT
 90 - 75 % GOOD
 75 - 50 % FAIR
 50 - 25 % POOR
 25 - 0 % VERY POOR

GROUND LEVEL: +2314.61 m.

DRILLHOLE LOCATION
 X=3087197.35
 Y=1239680.58
 Z=+2314.61

REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY ISLAMABAD	
SVECO STOCKHOLM AND PACIFIC CONSULTANTS INTERNATIONAL TOKYO	LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT DRILL HOLE D CORE LOG
95323	3 23

Level 0101 1117

REMARKS

DRILLHOLE LOCATION
X=3087490.860
Y=1237783.680
Z=+2659.270

Granodioritic type gray dark medium grained

WEATHERING
 W₁ = FRESH ROCK
 W₂ = WEATHERED
 W₃ = HIGHLY WEATHERED

JOINT FILLING DOMINATING
 Ca = CALCITE
 Cl = CLORITE
 Fe = IRON
 Ep = EPIDOT
 Qz = QUARTZ
 Cs = CLUCHEINSE

MOSTLY Cl - MOST FREQUENT
 JOINT FILLING MINERAL

POQ
 100 - 90 % EXCELLENT
 90 - 75 % GOOD
 75 - 50 % FAIR
 50 - 25 % POOR
 25 - 0 % VERY POOR

GROUND LEVEL -2659.27 m

DRILLHOLE LOCATION
 X=3087490.860
 Y=1237783.680
 Z=+2659.270

REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN		ISLAMABAD
NATIONAL HIGHWAY AUTHORITY		ISLAMABAD
SWECO	STOCKHOLM	LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
AND		DRILL HOLE E
PACIFIC CONSULTANTS		CORE LOG
INTERNATIONAL	TOKYO	
95323		11 07

LOWARAI TUNNEL ORGANIZATION (GEOTECH DTE) SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Sheet 1 of 18
HOLE: LTB2

Project: LOWARAI TUNNEL Site: SHAFT-1 Location: Dare khawar Date Started: Date Completed:
 Type of Boring: ROTARY Coordinates: Angle: VERTICAL Bearing:
 Ground Elev: 9040' Top of Rock Elev: 8990' Water Elev: Final Depth: 699'3"
 Contractor: GSP Driller: MAKHDOOM Finalized: SAEED Logged:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15				
Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Muds	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test		REMARKS			
														Duration (hrs)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (G/PM)		
0					○	Over-burden consists of angular to subangular boulders and pieces of Granodiorite, Amphibolite and Diorite with fine dark brown sandy silt (Black Mt)		BX size Diamond Bit Double Tube		NX	Hole cemented	Bentonite with water	100%	loss	No test performed			
5					○													
10					○													
15					○													
20					○													
25					○													
30					○													
35					○													
40					○													
45					○													
50					○													
55					○													
60					○													
65					○													
70					○													
75					○													
80					○													
85					○													
90					○													
95					○													
100					○													

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Massive > 4'
- Slightly 3-4'
- Moderately 6"-3'
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly > 6"
- Moderately 4'-6"
- Slightly < 4"

BX size Diamond Pit & Double Tube

BX

100% cemented

1955

100% Diamond

100%

100%

100%

100%

100%

100%

100%

100%

100%

39

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

LTB-2
4/18

3-2-5

Hole No. L7B-2
Sheet 6 of 18

Granodiorite
Same as above

Granodiorite
Same, but massive

Amphibolite, grey, fine grained,
hard.

BX size Diamond Bit & Double Tube

BX

Hole cemented

water

50% water loss

No Test performed

at 210'
30 vertical
filled with
Gauge

35

JA

20

35
20

100% 100% 100% 100%

Granodiorite
 Same, but
 Medium grained + veins of
 feldspar

Same as above,
 intercalation of amphi-
 bole and feldspar

15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2
U	S	JA	S	F	C	B							
39.50'	39.26'	39.13'	39.00'	38.87'	38.74'	38.61'	38.48'	38.35'	38.22'	38.09'	37.96'	37.83'	37.70'

Bx size Diamond Bit & Double Tube

Bx

Hole cemented

No. 1241 performed

Same as above

Amphibolite

GRANDIORITE

Hard to moderately hard,
fresh to slightly weathered,
coarse to fine grained gray-
ish white in colour, closely
jointed, slightly fractured,
moderately fractured at ph-
ases. Highly sheared & weath-
ered between 350 & 381 ft.

Grandiorite
Same as above

BX size Diamond Bit & Double Tube

BX

Hole cemented

50% water loss

No test performed

60°
35°
75°
49°
15°
31°
27°
15°

JA
B
JA

15

14

13

12

11

10

9

8

7

6

5

4

3

2

1

1	2.2	4.5	6	Granddiprite Same as above 7.8		
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
15						

4 BXW size Diamond Bit & Double Tube

Hole cemented

Water

50% loss

No Test performed

JA

JA

02

J

D

JA

6.4 26°

4.3 39°

2.9 17°

3.5 17°
5.6 28°
3.4 34°

Sheet 13 of 18

Hole No. LT B 2

Same as above
 Granddiorite
 P-8

Hole 1-11-13 2

Sheet 14 of 15

8' 9" 14' 10" 14' 14' 15'

630
625
620
615
610
605
600
595
590

80%
86%
100%
6d
70%
52%
57%

Amphibolite
Same as above P. 8
Granodiorite

Bxmsize Diamond Bit & Double Tube

Hole cemented

100% water loss

No test performed

JA

JA

47°

101
No.

30
13
22

7
B
9
10
11
12
13
14
15

SHEET - 1

GROUND ELEVATION:
2680.309

F&W ENGINEERS GROUP LTD.
Foundation & Water Management Engg. Group Ltd.
Geotechnical Engineers

PROJECT:LOWARI TUNNEL
PROJECT.

CLIENT : NATIONAL HIGHWAY BOARD.

LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF
SHARAI GOL.

CONSULTANTS : ENGINEERING CONSULTANTS.

BOREHOLE NO. LTB-4.

GWC WATER TABLE	DEPTH	THICKNESS	STRATA ENCOUNTERED	SYMBOLS	RECOVERY %	REMARKS	
	(m)	(m)					
	0.0						
	0.60	0.60	Brown firm slightly plastic CLAYEY SILT with boulders, cobbles and gravel of granite. Brown, stiff, low plastic clayey SILT with gravel, cobbles and traces of fine sand-			Percussion boring with 14"Ø bailer and 16"Ø casing upto 5.0 metres depth.	
	4.60	4.00					
	5.00	0.40	Yellowish brown sandy silty CLAY with gravel and cobbles. Light grey, moderately hard GRAVEL & COBBLES with association of fine sand.			Rotary drilling from 5.0 meters and N casing upto 14.20 meters.	
	6.20	7.80					42
	7.00						12
	8.00						30
	8.80						25
	9.30						90
	10.00						43
	10.60						33
	11.00						75
	12.00						33
	12.80			50	100% water loss from 11.0 meters.		
	14.50	3.20	Dark grey fine SAND associated with loosely packed gravels and cobbles.			Water loss controlled due to casing upto 14.20 meters.	
	16.00						12
						contd. on sheet 2.	

TYPE OF DRILLING : PERCUSSION/ROTARY.

DEPTH OF BOREHOLE : 60 meters.

GROUND WATER TABLE: 48 meters.

DATE OF START : 28/09/87

DATE OF COMPLETION : 20/11/87.

[Signature]
GEOLOGIST/ENGINEER

CLIENT REP.

SHEET - 2

GROUND ELEVATION:
2680.309

F&W ENGINEERS GROUP LTD.
Foundation & Water Management Engg. Group Ltd.
Geotechnical Engineers

PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL
PROJECT.

CLIENT : NATIONAL HIGHWAY BOARD

LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF
SHARAI GOL.

CONSULTANTS : ENGINEERING CONSULTANTS.

BOREHOLE NO. LTB - 4.

G.W. TABLE (E)	DEPTH	THICKNESS	STRATA ENCOUNTERED	SYMBOLS	RECOVERY %	REMARKS	
	(m)	(m)					
	16.0		Dark grey fine SAND associated with loosely packed gravel and cobbles.			50% water loss.	
	17.50	13.85			13		
	20.50				06		
	22.00				10		
	23.50				06		
	25.00				NIL		
	26.50				06		
	28.85				NIL		
	29.85				10		
	32.00				2.15		Grey moderately hard GRAVEL & COBBLES intermixed with fine to medium sand, loosely packed, moderately weathered to highly weathered and deteriorated.

CONTD. ON SHEET 3.

TYPE OF DRILLING : PERCUSSION/ROTARY.

DEPTH OF BOREHOLE : 60 meters.

DATE OF START : 28/09/87.

GROUND WATER TABLE: 48 meters.

DATE OF COMPLETION : 20/11/87.

[Signature]
GEOLOGIST/ENGINEER

CLIENT REP.

GROUND ELEVATION:
2680.309

F&W ENGINEERS GROUP LTD.
Foundation & Water Management Engg. Group Ltd.
Geotechnical Engineers

PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL
PROJECT.

CLIENT : NATIONAL HIGHWAY BOARD

LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF
SHARAI GOL.

CONSULTANTS : ENGINEERING CONSULTANTS

BOREHOLE NO. LTB - 4.

GRC WATER TABLE	DEPTH	THICKNESS	STRATA ENCOUNTERED	SYMBOLS	RECOVERY %	REMARKS
	(m)	(m)				
	32.0					
	32.85	5.35	Grey moderately hard GRAVEL & COBBLES intermixed with fine to medium sand, loosely packed, moderately weathered to lightly weathered and deteriorated.		NIL	Water loss 20%-70%
	34.35				10	
	37.35				51	
	37.75	2.25	Grey, moderately hard BOULDERS and COBBLES of granitic origin with few pieces of deteriorated gravel.		37	20% water loss.
	39.60				80	
	40.75	5.75	Grey, soft to moderately hard fine to coarse grained GRAVEL intermixed with fine sand and occasional cobbles.		40	Water loss 15% to 20%
	42.35				16	
	45.35				13	
	48.00	2.65	Grey, hard GRAVEL and COBBLES of granitic origin intermixed with fine gravel.		25	Water loss 10% to 20%

CONTD. ON SHEET - 4.

TYPE OF DRILLING : PERCUSSION/ROTARY.

DEPTH OF BOREHOLE : 60 meters.

DATE OF START : 280987.

GROUND WATER TABLE: 48 meters.

DATE OF COMPLETION : 201187.

[Signature]
GEOLOGIST/ENGINEER

CLIENT REP.

SHEET - 4.

GROUND ELEVATION:
2680.309

F&W ENGINEERS GROUP LTD.
Foundation & Water Management Engg. Group Ltd.
Geotechnical Engineers

PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL
PROJECT.

LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF
SHARAI GOL.

CLIENT : NATIONAL HIGHWAY BOARD.

BOREHOLE NO. LTB - 4.

CONSULTANTS : ENGINEERING CONSULTANTS.

GROUND WATER TABLE	DEPTH	THICKNESS	STRATA ENCOUNTERED	SYMBOLS	RECOVERY %	REMARKS
	(m)	(m)				
48.0	48.40	4.80	Grey hard GRAVEL and COBBLES of grainitic origin intermixed with fine gravel.		38	10% to 20% water loss.
	50.40				30	
	52.80				31	
	55.80	3.00	Grey hard BOULDERS and COBBLES of grainitic origin associated with fine gravel.		33	Water loss 10%
	58.80	3.00	Blackish grey, moderately hard coarse grained GRAVEL intermixed with fine gravel and fine sand.		07	15% water loss.
	60.00	1.20	Greyish black hard BOULDERS & COBBLES of grainitic origin associated with fine sand.		58	Water loss 10%
			END OF BOREHOLE.			

TYPE OF DRILLING : PERCUSSION/ROTARY.

DEPTH OF BOREHOLE : 60 meters.

GROUND WATER TABLE: 48 meters.

DATE OF START : 28/09/87

DATE OF COMPLETION : 20/11/87.

GEOLOGIST/ENGINEER

CLIENT REP.

ANNEXURE NO. 3

- 8.0 LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS
- 8.1 GRAIN SIZE ANALYSES
- 8.2 ATTERBERG LIMITS
- 8.3 NATURAL MOISTURE CONTENT
- 8.4 DIRECT SHEAR TEST
- 8.5 RELATIVE DENSITY
- 8.6 UNCONFINED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH
- 8.7 SPECIFIC GRAVITY
- 8.8 POROSITY
- 8.9 ABSORPTION
- 8.10 DRY UNIT WEIGHT
- 8.11 POINT LOAD INDEX
- 8.12 MODULUS OF ELASTICITY

ASTM Laboratories

ASSOCIATED EDIL & TESTING MATERIAL LABS.
 25-A, MEHAR MADALI HOUSING SOCIETY,
 SEVEN MARRIAGES LANE KARACHI - PAKISTAN

PHONES 437779
 437856

CLIENT : F&W ENGINEERS (PVT) LTD.,
 PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL.
 LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF SHAFI GOL.

DATED 31/12/87. L.R. NO. 0001920/21/87

GRAIN SIZE ANALYSIS (% FINER WEIGHT).

B.H.	DEPTH	SAMPLE	3"	2½"	2"	1½"	1"	¾"	½"	3/8"	#4	#8	#16	#30	#50	100	200	0.075	0.075	0.075	0.075
LIB 1	0.0 - 0.60 m.	DS	100	50.7	29.3	-	-	21.4	18.6	17.2	15.3	14.8	13.9	13.5	12.8	12.3	11.6	-	-	-	-
LIB 2	0.60 - 4.60 m.	DS	-	-	-	100	71.2	55.2	52.5	49.2	45.1	44.1	42.4	41.7	40.3	39.7	39.0	29.6	7.8	-	-
LIB 3	4.60 - 5.00 m.	DS	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	94.2	78.2	71.8	63.5	61.0	56.5	54.5	52.3	44.9	30.5	21.8	10.4

SIZE-INCHES

U. S. STANDARD SIEVE SIZE

ASTM Laboratories

ASSOCIATED SOIL & TESTING MATERIAL LABS
 1-A, MOHAMMAD ALI HOUSING SOCIETY
 FF SHAHRAH-E-FAISAL, KARACHI-8 PAKISTAN

PHONE. 437779
 437956

DATE. 26/12/87.

LR NO. 00000021/87

CLIENT: M/s. F&W Engineers Group (pvt) Ltd.

PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL.

LOCATION: Right Bank of Sharai Gol.

BH NO.	DEPTH	SAMPLE	ATTERBERG LL	LIMIT PI	N.M.C. %	WET DENSITY gm/cc	DRY DENSITY gm/cc	DIRECT SHEAR C(kg/cm ²) φ	RELATIVE DENSITY. BASED ON NATURAL DENSITY.
LTB-4	0.0-0.6	DS	N.P.	N.P.	10.1	-	-	-	54.8
LTB-4	0.6-4.6	DS	21.0	5.6	15.3	-	-	-	-
LTB-4	4.6-5.0	DS	29.2	13.2	27.7	-	-	0.20 23°	-

for ASTM LABORATORIES.

ASTM Laboratories

ASSOCIATED SOIL & TESTING MATERIAL LABS
28-A, MOHAMMAD ALI HOUSING SOCIETY
OFF SHAHRAH-E-FAISAL, KARACHI-8 PAKISTAN

PHONE. 437779
437956

CLIENT. M/S F&W ENGINEERS GROUP (PVT) LTD.

PROJECT: LOWARI TUNNEL.

LOCATION. RIGHT BANK OF SHARAI GOL.

DATED. 31.12.87

L2 = 0001920/21/87

(PHYSICAL TEST ON)
CORE.

BH NO.	DEPTH IN (M)	UN-COMFIED COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH IN PSI.	SP.GRAVITY.	POROSITY %	ABSORPTION %	DRY UNIT WT (gm/cc)	POINT LOAD TEST IN PSI
LTB . 4	5.0 - 6.20	5800	2.73	34	0.504	1.79	-
LTB . 4	7.0 - 8.00	-	2.68	33	0.688	1.77	414.8
LTB . 4	9.30-10.00	6697	2.67	33	0.556	1.77	-
LTB . 4	12.00-12.80	7850	2.80	35	0.429	1.81	543.2
LTB . 4	14.50-16.00	-	2.79	33	0.423	1.85	-
LTB . 4	34.35-37.35	7200	2.80	33	0.454	1.88	493.8
LTB . 4	46.40-50.40	-	2.72	34	0.247	1.79	395.06
LTB . 4	52.80-55.80	6660	2.80	36	0.254	1.83	375.3
LTB . 4	58.80-60.00	7326	2.82	32	0.229	1.93	474.07

ASTM Laboratories

ASSOCIATED SOIL & TESTING MATERIAL LABS
1-A, MOHAMMAD ALI HOUSING SOCIETY
OFF SHAHRAH-E-FAISAL, KARACHI-8 PAKISTAN

DATE: 31/12/87.

CLIENT: M/S F&W ENGINEERS (PVT) LTD.
PROJECT: LOWARI, TUNNEL.
LOC: RIGHT BANK OF SHARAI GOL.

<u>B.H. NO.</u>	<u>DEPTH IN METRES.</u>	<u>MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (E)</u>
LTB. - 4	7.00 - 8.00	63462
LTB. - 4	14.50 - 16.00	61538
LTB - 4	48.40 - 50.40	59259
LTB - 4	58.80 - 60.00	135000

for ASTM LABORATORIES.

MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (E) = 30,000,000 PSI
 MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (E) = 63,462 PSI

CLIENT: M/S. FSN ENGINEERS GROUP (PVT) LTD.
 PROJECT: TOWARD TUNNEL
 LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF SHARAI COL.
 BH. NO. 11B, 4
 DEPTH: 1.0-8.0 M

MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (E) = 6000000 PSI
 0100975
 1581538 PSI

CLIENT: M/S IAW ENGINEERS GROUP (PVT) LTD.
 PROJECT: TOWARI TUNNEL
 LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF SHARAI COL.
 BH NO: 118-7
 DEPTH: 14.50 - 16.00 M

MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (MPa) = $\frac{59259}{0.00075} = 78678666.67$

CLIENT: M/S. FAW ENGINEERS GROUP (PVT) LTD.
 PROJECT: TOWARI TUNNEL
 LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF SAHAYI COL.
 BH. NO: 1111/7
 DEPTH: 8.70 - 50.70 M

MODULUS OF ELASTICITY (E) = $\frac{1.35 \times 10^6}{0.005} = 2.7 \times 10^8$ PSI

CLIENT: M/S. P&W ENGINEERS GROUP (PVT) LTD.
 PROJECT: TOWARDI TUNNEL
 LOCATION: RIGHT BANK OF SHARAI GOL.

BR. NO. 134
 DEPTH: 50.00 - 60.00 M

BOREHOLE LOGS

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LOWARI TUNNEL Site _____ Location ZIARAT Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600' Above Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 190.5'
 Contractor W.A.P.D.A. Driller M. Khan Inspector _____ Logged Aghar Hamid
 Finalized: Ejaz Imami

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS		
													Duration (Mts)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)			
19						<u>OPEN PIT..</u> <u>Consisting of Silty Sand and brown loose soil.</u>												
76						<u>VOLCANIC BASIC ROCK:</u> <u>Dark grey-greenish, hard, fine grained basic rock, slightly metamorphosed, regularly bedded, severely crushed and pulverized, mylonitized and contains Quartz veinlets at places.</u>		<u>86 mm diam bit, D.T., Core barrel.</u>										
6.0																		
2.6	100																	
93																		
10.2																		
71																		
11.7																		
2.7	100																	
8.7	100																	
14.7	100																	
82																		
17.2	100																	
91																		
20.6																		
95																		
22.2																		
76																		
24.4																		
92																		
27.4																		
29.6	100																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

MAHI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LOWARI TUNNEL Site _____ Location Ziarot Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600' Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 190-5
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Inspector _____ Logged Asghar Hamid
 Finalized: Ejaz Imami

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS													
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)														
30						Same as above																							
35	52 60 71					GRANO-DIORITE GNEISS: Dark ~ dark green, fine grained, hard, Compact, gneissic with porphyritic texture spotted with coarser hornblend crystals, mostly un-weathered, slightly ~ moderately jointed.	76mm Diamond Bit	D.T. Core Barrell					100	100	100														
40	100																												
45	100																												
50	100																												
55	96																												
	94																												
	100																												
	100																												
	100																												
60	100																												

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

IMAMI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LOWARI Pass Site _____ Location Ziarat Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600' Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 190'-5"
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Finalized: Ejaz Imami Logged Aghar Hamid

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium:	Water Test			REMARKS				
												Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)		Water Loss (GPM)			
60	100																		
65	100																		
70	83					<p><u>VOLCANIC BASIC ROCK:</u> Dark grey ~ greenish, hard, fine grained, slightly metamorphosed, regularly bedded, severely crushed and pulverized, mylonitized and contains Quartz veinlets at places.</p>													
75	100																		
80	95																		
85	100																		
90	83																		

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

IMAMI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LOWARI TUNNEL Site _____ Location ZIARAT Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7500' Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 190'-5"
 Contractor WAPDA Driller M. Khan Finalized: Ejaz Mami Logged Asghar Hamid

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
90	100					Same as above											
95	100																
100	100																
105	100																
110	100																
115	100																
120	100																

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

MAMI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lahori Tunnel Site _____ Location Ziarat Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600' Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 190'-5"
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Finalized: Ejaz Inami Logged Agher Hamid

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Mins.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
120	100					Same as above											
125	100																
130	100																
135	100																
140	100																
145	100																
150	100																

<p>WEATHERING</p> <p> Slightly</p> <p> Moderately</p> <p> Highly</p>	<p>JOINT SPACING</p> <p> Sparsely > 12"</p> <p> Moderately 6" To 12"</p> <p> Closely < 6"</p>	<p>FRAGMENTATION</p> <p> Slightly 50% > 6"</p> <p> Moderately 50% 4" To 6"</p> <p> Highly 50% < 4"</p>
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SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lahari Tunnel Site _____ Location Ziarat Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600' Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 190-5
 Contractor Napda Driller M. Khan Finalized: Ejaz Imami Logged Asghar Hamid

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS		
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)			
150	100					Same as above												
155	100																	
160	100																	
165	100																	
170	100																	
175	100																	
180	100																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

IMAMI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Londri Tunnel Site _____ Location Ziarat Date Started _____ Date Completed _____
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 7600 Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 190'-5"
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Finalized: Gias / mam Logged Asghar Hamid

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)	
180	100					Same as above		76 mm - Diam. Bit D.T. Core Barrel	N I L	N I L	W A T E R					
185	100															
190	14	Crushed				Bottom of hole.										

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lahori Tunnel Site L.T. Tunnel Location Near Mirza Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 8080 Appx Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 207'
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Finalized by G. J. Imami Logged M. R. Zaidi

Depth (Ft)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS
													Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)	
0						<u>OPEN PIT.</u> Consisting of Silty Sand and brown loose soil.		<u>86mm MX-Single Tube</u>								
5						<u>GRANITE:-</u> Dirty white with black coloured specks, coarse grained, hard, massive, consisting of mica, feldspar, quartz and limonite, sparsely jointed, joint-planes stained with iron, slightly weathered.		<u>86mm-D/B-RIT B/P</u>								
10						<u>GRANO-DIORITE:-</u> Dirty white ~ dark grey, medium grained, hard, compact, massive, consisting of mica, feldspar, quartz, hornblend and iron ore. Sparsely jointed, joints 40° ~ 80° to core axis, iron stained, generally fresh.		<u>76mm-Diamond Bit - Double Tube & B.P.</u>	<u>NIL</u>	<u>NIL</u>	<u>T</u>	<u>E</u>	<u>60 ~ 70</u>			
15									<u>NIL</u>	<u>NIL</u>	<u>A</u>	<u>Y</u>				
20									<u>NIL</u>	<u>NIL</u>	<u>W</u>					
25																
30																

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

Imami

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lodari Tunnel Site LT Tunnel Location Near Mirza Khaner
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Ground Elev. 8000-8000 Top of Rock Elev _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Contractor Alpda Driller M. Khan Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 207'
 Finalized: E. MAMI Logged M.R. Zaidi

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS			
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)				
30	95																		
35	95																		
40	100																		
45	100																		
50	100																		
55	95																		
60	95																		

76mm - Diamond Bit - D/H & B/D
 NIL
 NIL
 W A T E R

- WEATHERING**
- Slightly
 - Moderately
 - Highly

- JOINT SPACING**
- Sparsely > 12"
 - Moderately 6" To 12"
 - Closely < 6"

- FRAGMENTATION**
- Slightly 50% > 6"
 - Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
 - Highly 50% < 4"

7042-D-4052

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LAHARI TUNNEL Site LT. Tunnel Location Near Mirka Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates KANAY Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 2000-44 Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 207'
 Contractor Nabha Driller M. Khan Finalized by E. Imami Logged M. R. Zaidi

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS		
													Duration (Min)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)			
60	100					<p>GRAN-DIORITE Pinkish white, med. grained hard, compact, massive. Consisting of feldspar, quartz, mica, hornblend etc. Sparsely jointed, fresh, joint planes at places leached.</p>												
65	98																	
70	100																	
75	91																	
80	95																	
85	96																	
90	85																	
	99																	

76mm - Diamond Bit - Double Tube Bottom Discharge
 N I L
 N I L
 W A T E R
 N I L

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Fragmentation 1
- Fragmentation 2
- Fragmentation 3

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LONARI TUNNEL Site LT. TUNNEL Location NEAR MIRA KHANAY Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle VERTICAL Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 8000-Appx. Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 207'
 Contractor Napda Driller M. Khan Analyst E. IMAMI Logged M.R. Zaidi

Depth (ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)	
98						<p><u>GRAN-DIORITE:-</u> Same as above but Dirty White, med. grained, massive, Compact & fresh. Quartz veins and pyrite crystals also present in small quantity along joint planes, Sparsely jointed.</p>		<p>76mm - Diamond Bit - Double Tube - Bottom Discharge.</p>								
95																
96																
100																
100																
105																
100																
90																
110																
115																
100																
100																
720																

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

IMAMI

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LONARI TUNNEL Site LT. TUNNEL Location Near Mirza Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates 24° 20' N Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 8000-APP Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 207'
 Contractor WAPDA Driller M. Khan Finalized: E. MAMI Logged M.R. ZAIDI

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS		
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)			
120																		
125																		
130																		
135																		
140																		
145																		
150																		

56 mm Diamond Bit, Single Tube.
 N I L
 N I L
 N A T E R
 N I L

WEATHERING Slightly Moderately Highly	JOINT SPACING Sparsely > 12" Moderately 6" To 12" Closely < 6"	FRAGMENTATION Slightly 50% > 6" Moderately 50% 4" To 6" Highly 50% < 4"
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Hole No. LT-2
 Sheet 6 of 7

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lasari Tunnel Site LT Tunnel Location Near Muz Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 900-000 Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 202'
 Contractor Wapda Driller M. Khan Finalized: E. Imami Logged M.R. Zaidi

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium:	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS			
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)				
150																			
155	90																		
160	97																		
165	100																		
170	98																		
175	72																		
180	80																		

56 mm - Diamond Bit - Single Tube.

NIL
 NIL
 WATER
 NIL

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

IMAMI

Form FMS-2
 PLANNING AND INVESTIGATION DIRECTORATE
 WAPDA, WEST PAKISTAN

Hole No. LT-14
 Sheet 7 of 7

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project LOWARI TUNNEL Site LT. TUNNEL Location Near Mirza Khan Date Started 21.7.65 Date Completed 7.10.65
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 8000-115 Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 207
 Contractor WAPDA Driller M. Khan Finalized E. MAM Logged M. R. ZAIDI

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
185	100																
190	98																
195	98																
200	100																
205	100																
207	100																
Hole Completed at 207 ft.																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

MAM

Hole No. LT-3

Sheet 2 of 10

7042-D-4053

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass. Site Lowari Village Location Dare Khwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Zahoor A. Logged Zahoor Ahmad

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium:	Water Test			REMARKS
												Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	
0						open Pit. over burden boulders, gravels, Clay and sand.			Casing						
10						<u>OVER BURDEN:-</u> Loose Sand and granitic Gneiss boulders, pebbles and gravel. At places core from boulders recovered.		86 M.M. Double tube core barrel. Diamond bit.							No pressure tests were performed in this borehole
20															
30															

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

Finalized by

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass Site Lowari Village Location Dorekhuwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 320'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Zahoor Ahmad Logged Zahoor Ahmad

Depth (ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
30						<u>over burden:-</u> Loose sand, granitic gneiss boulders, gravel etc. as above. from 49'-51' full core recovery from a granite gneiss boulders.		86 M.M. double tube core barrel diamond bit									
40																	
50																	
70						<u>Dolerite :-</u> Whitish grey, hard, compact, acidic metamorphic rock. felspar streaks. mica (black) flakes noticeable. Highly fragmented size $\angle 6^\circ$. Closely jointed. With angles 25° - 30° , 45° and 60° - 70° with Core-Axis. Slightly weathered.		76 M.M. D.T.C.B. di. bit									
100																	
60																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6°
- Moderately 50% 4° To 6°
- Highly 50% < 4°

Finalized by

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass Site Lowari Village Location Darikhwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Zaboor Ahmad Logged Zaboor Ahmad

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium:	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Mins.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
60	92					<u>Dolerite:-</u> <u>light grey, hard, acidic, metamorphosed rock. Highly fragmented and closely jointed, with angles 15-20°, 45° and 60-70° with core-axis. Slightly weathered at joint faces.</u>											
70	100					<u>Same as above in all respect.</u>											
75	100					<u>Same as above and joint faces coated with green streaks of hornblende.</u>											
80	100					<u>Same as above, med. to fine grained quartz-felspathic rock.</u>											
85	95					<u>Same as above, in all respect. joint faces coated with green amphiboles, and yellow iron oxide. feldspar grains visible.</u>											
90	100					<u>As above Dolerite fine to med. grained, hard metamorphosed rock. Highly fragmented and closely jointed.</u>											
90	100					<u>Same as above, rock in all respect, but no green material coating on joint planes.</u>											

76 M.M. double tube core barrel - Diamond bit.

From 85 to 100' Complete loss of drilling water. nearly 13-gall per min.

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

Finalized by

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass. Site Lowari Village Location Dare Khwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Zahoor Ahmad Logged Zahoor Ahmad

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS		
													Duration (Mins.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)			
50						Dolerite - same as above. Highly fragmented and jointed closely with angles 65°-75° with core-axis.												
98						Same as above.												
98						Dolerite. Same in all respect. Jointing angles 5°, 20-25°, 45-60° to core-axis.												
100						Same as above.												
100						As above in all respect.												
100						As above Dolerite. White sandy material coated on joint faces. Highly fragmented and closely jointed.												
110						Same as above in all respect. but med. & highly fragmented and med. jointed.												
120						Same as above in all respect. Highly jointed and fragmented joint angles 5-10°, 20-30°, 40°, and 65-70° with C-axis.												
120						Same as above.												

WEATHERING

	Slightly
	Moderately
	Highly

JOINT SPACING

	Sparsely	> 12"
	Moderately	6" To 12"
	Closely	< 6"

FRAGMENTATION

	Slightly	50% > 6"
	Moderately	50% 4" To 6"
	Highly	50% < 4"

Finalized by
[Signature]

Hole No. LT-3
 Sheet 5 of 10

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass Site Lowari Village Location Dore Khwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Zahoor Ahmad Logged Zahoor Ahmad

Depth (Ft)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
120	100					Dolerite Rock. Light grey fine med. grained. hard. Highly fragmented. Closely jointed with angles 5-10°, 20-30°, 40° and 65-70° with c-axis. fresh.											
	100					Same as above in all respect.			L								
130	100					Same as above.			L								
	100					As above.			L								
	95					Same as above.			E								
	100					Same as above.											
140	100					Dolerite: whitish powdery material coated on joint faces. jointing angles same as above.			I								
	100					Same as above. joint angles 20-30° and 40-45° with c-axis.			A								
	96					Same as above. joint angles 5-10° and 30° to c-axis.			N								
	100					Same as above in all respect.			N								
150																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6°
- Moderately 50% 4° To 6°
- Highly 50% < 4°

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SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass Site Lowari Village Location Dare Khann Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. _____ Top of Rock Elev _____ Gr. Water Elev _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Sahoor Ahmed Logged Sahoor Ahmed

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test		REMARKS	
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)		Water Loss (GPM)
150	100					As above quartz-fels pathic rock.										
150	100					Biotite-Granite in bluish grey med. to coarse grained, dark minerals oriented in foliation direction, hard rock. Slightly fragmented and jointed along foliation direction. fresh.										
150	100					As above, but from 156.6' to 156.9' patch of dark band, i.e. dioritic or granite gneiss. Pyroxene, olivine noticed in the rock dark band, near 157'. Quartz-fels pathic rock here is mixed with Granodiorite.										
150	100					Dioritic rock with darker appearance, with dark minerals in abundance, i.e. pyroxene, amphibole and biotite. Slightly fragmented, sparsely jointed with angles 5-10° and 20-25° with core-axis, fresh.										
160	100					Same as above, upto 168' thin Granite Gneiss; whitish, with dark minerals (biotite + hornblende) along foliation, mod. fragmented, sparsely jointed, angles 5-10° & 40-45° with core-axis, fresh.										
160	100					Same as above in all respect mod. jointed, with angles 5-10° 30°, 45° and parallel to core axis. Slightly to mod. fragmented, fresh.										
170	100					As above, one joint parallel to c-axis from 171-180' and one 30° to core axis, mod. fragmented, fresh.										
180	100															

156.6' to 168' in Dioritic rock with dark minerals in abundance, med. to coarse grained.

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

Finalized by

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Loonax Pass Site Loonax Village Location Darkhwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 867.2 Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 300
 Contractor D. I. D. Wapda Driller Fahon Shah Inspector Rahoor Ahmad Logger Fahon Ahmad

Depth (Ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbol	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test			REMARKS	
													Duration (Min.)	Pressure (PSI)	Water Loss (GPM)		
180						<p><u>Granite Gneiss whitish grey med. to coarse grained. biotite and hornblende poorly aligned parallel to foliation. mod. fragmented sparsely to mod. jointed with angles 5-10, 25-30° and parallel to c-axis. 187.6' to 211' Diorite + Grano diorite. dark minerals in abundance i.e. rock is dark coloured with quartz and fels par as bluish spots. Slightly fragmented. sparsely jointed parallel to c-axis to vein of quartz filled. fresh.</u></p> <p><u>Same as above. Slightly fragmented. sparsely jointed with angles 5-10, 45° and 65-70° to core axis. fresh.</u></p> <p><u>Diorite + Grano diorite as above. 198-198.6' pinkish felspar is in abundance. biotite is also in abundance at places. Quartz or felspar concentrated bands are frequent like a pegmatitic lense. foliation is poorly developed. Slightly to mod. fragmented. Sparsely to mod. jointed. fresh.</u></p> <p><u>Same as above. one joint 1' felspar filled with 5-10' with c-axis. Slightly fragmented. Sparsely jointed. fresh.</u></p> <p><u>Same as above.</u></p>											
100																	
45																	
190																	
100																	
200																	
100																	
210																	

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

Finalized

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Lowari Pass Site Lowari Village Location Darre Khwar Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Ground Elev. 359.2 Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 300'
 Contractor D.I.D. Wapda Driller Ehsan Shah Inspector Fakoor Ahmad Logged Fakoor Ahmad

Depth (ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbols	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test		REMARKS	
													Duration (Min)	Pressure (PSI)		Water Loss (GPM)
270						Granite diorite + Diorite - Med. to coarse grained, hard dark minerals in abundance. i.e. hornblende, biotite etc. Sparsely jointed, filled with quartz (silica) with angle 5-10° & parallel to core axis. joints are tight, mod. fragmented fresh.										
250						Same as above, but with few soft zones, which has been washed away during drilling. Sparsely jointed with angle 5° to core axis. Slightly fragmented.										
240						Same as above in all respect.										
230						Same as above but few magmatic bands noted, and quartz veinlets also noted. Sparsely jointed. few joints are quartz filled with angles 5-10°, 25-30°, 45°, and parallel to core axis. Mod. fragmented. Slightly weathered at places.										
220						Same as above 225 to 265 are more in lay, rest 265-267 is 1/2 decomposed and weathered mass.										
210						Same as above. Quartz veinlets and bands (lenses) noted. Mod jointed with angles 25-30°, 5-10°, 45° to core axis.										

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 30% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

finalized by

FMS-2
PLANNING AND INVESTIGATION DIRECTORATE
W.P.A. WEST PAKISTAN

Hole No. LFJ
Sheet 31 of 10

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION LOG

Project Dosare Pass Site Dosare Village Location Darekhan Date Started 18.9.71 Date Completed 31.10.71
 Type of Boring Rotary Coordinates _____ Angle Vertical Bearing _____
 Elevation 8592.1 Top of Rock Elev. _____ Gr. Water Elev. _____ Final Depth 300
 Contractor D.I.D. AOB DA Driller Fahsan Shah Inspector Jahoor Ahmad Logged Jahoor Ahmad

Depth (ft.)	Core Recovery (%)	Weathering	Jointing	Fragmentation	Lithic Symbols	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	Sample for Testing	Sampler & Bit	Casing Type	Hole Cemented	Drilling Medium	Drilling Fluid Recovery (%)	Water Test		REMARKS	
													Duration (Mts.)	Pressure (PSI)		Water Loss (GPM)
270	90					Coarse granite + Diorite: med. to coarse grained, dark minerals abundant. Same as from 280 to 270. Highly fragmented and jointed.										Core from 278 to 280' mainly washed in filter
280	50					Granite Gneiss: white med. to coarse grained. Highly fragmented and jointed with angles 5-10°, 20-30° & 45° to core axis.										
285	30					As above white granite. feldspar and quartz dominant. med. fragmented, and med. jointed with angles 5-10° and parallel to core axis. fresh.										
290	75					Same as above white granite was encountered, bearing to med. jointed with angles 5-10° and parallel to core axis. med. fragmented. fresh.										
295	90					Same as above in all respect.										
300	60					Same as above in all respect. white, med. to coarse grained granite. foliation not clear. Sparsely jointed with angles 5-10° & parallel to core axis. Slightly fragmented. fresh.										Hole Completed at 300'

WEATHERING

- Slightly
- Moderately
- Highly

JOINT SPACING

- Sparsely > 12"
- Moderately 6" To 12"
- Closely < 6"

FRAGMENTATION

- Slightly 50% > 6"
- Moderately 50% 4" To 6"
- Highly 50% < 4"

finalized by
[Signature]

7042-D-4054

Bore Hole

No. ET-3

Box No. 4/16

Depth: 0'-37"

DESCR

Box No. - 2/16

Depth: - 37'-61"

Box No. 3/16

Depth: - 61'-75"

DREAM

HOW

MOTAT

Box No. 4/16

Depth: - 75' - 89'

Box No. 5/16

Depth: - 89' - 103'

Box No. 6/16

Depth: - 103' - 116'

Box No. 7/16
Depth: 116'-130'

Box No. 7/16
Depth:- 116'-130'

Box No. 8/16
Depth: 130'-143'

Box No. 8/16
Depth:- 130'-143'

Box No. 9/16
Depth: 143'-155'

Box 9/16
Depth:- 143'-155'

Box No. 16/16

Depth:- 267'-300'

LEGEND

- ===== EXISTING UNMETALLED ROAD
- ~~~~~ STREAM
- CONTOUR WITH ELEVATION
- - - - - PROPOSED TUNNEL ALIGNMENT
- ==== PROPOSED ROAD
- 0 P SEISMIC LINE

NOTES

1. BASE MAP WITH CONTOURS WAS PROVIDED BY CLIENT
2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METERS
3. INTERPPETED SUBSURFACE SECTIONS ALONG SEISMIC LINES ARE SHOWN IN FIGS 2 THROUGH 10.

LOWAR TUNNEL PROJECT
 NORTH PORTAL AREA
 LOCATION PLAN OF
 SEISMIC LINES

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE REFER FIG 1

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE K-JI

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE REFER FIG 1

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE L-J2

FIG. 4.

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. 1.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE Q-R

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. 1.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE M-N

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. I.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE O - P

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE REFER FIG. 1.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE S-T

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. 1

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE Y-Z

NOTE:
FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. 1.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA
INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE V-X

NOTE:

FOR LOCATION OF SEISMIC LINE
REFER FIG. 1.

LOWARI TUNNEL PROJECT
NORTH PORTAL AREA

INTERPRETED SUBSURFACE SECTION
SEISMIC LINE F-G

VBB Anläggning AB, Stockholm

 Box 34044
 100 26 STOCKHOLM

<i>Client No:</i>	V0165
<i>Date of Arrival</i>	27 August, 1997
<i>Project No:</i>	21003014
<i>Station:</i>	Water
<i>Site:</i>	Pakistan
<i>Reference:</i>	Björn Collin
<i>Sample collector:</i>	Client

<i>Sample No:</i>	103388
<i>Sample label:</i>	Trangar Gol
<i>Sampling Date:</i>	1 August, 1997

Temperature*	°C	9	Chloride	mg/l	<1.0
Colour		5	Sulphate	mg/l	2.0
Colour/acidified*		5	Fluoride	mg/l	<0.10
Turbidity	FNU	2.7	Iron (B)	mg/l	<0.05
Turbidity/acidified*	FNU	1.8	Manganese (B)	mg/l	<0.01
Sediments		Little	Calcium (B)	mg/l	5.7
Odour (20°C)		Evident (Musty)	Magnesium (B)	mg/l	0.66
pH		6.9	Total Hardness (B)	°dH	0.95
Conductivity	mS/m	4.0	CO ₂ , aggr. to marble/calc.	mg/l	5
COD _{Mn}	mg/l	<1.0	Silica (B)	mg/l	4.2
Ammoniumnitrogen	mg/l	0.02	Potassium (B)	mg/l	0.20
Nitrate-nitrogen	mg/l	0.17	Sodium (B)	mg/l	1.5
Nitrite-nitrogen	mg/l	<0.002	Aluminium (B)	mg/l	0.12
Phosphate-phosphorous	mg/l	0.003	Copper (B)	mg/l	<0.01
Alkalinity	mg HCO ₃ /l	18	B: Digestion 0.34 M HNO ₃		-----

* Is not included in the accreditation or has not been performed by VVL.

 Stockholm 21 November, 1997
 Vattenvårdslaboratoriet

Ulla Rydevik

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VBB Anläggning AB, Stockholm

 Box 34044
 100 26 STOCKHOLM

<i>Client No:</i>	V0165
<i>Date of Arrival</i>	27 August, 1997
<i>Project No:</i>	21003014
<i>Station:</i>	Water
<i>Site:</i>	Pakistan
<i>Reference:</i>	Björn Collin
<i>Sample collector:</i>	Client

<i>Sample No:</i>	103389
<i>Sample label:</i>	Mirga Khwar
<i>Sampling Date:</i>	1 August, 1997

Temperature*	°C	10	Chloride	mg/l	<1.0
Colour		5	Sulphate	mg/l	2.0
Colour/acidified*		5	Fluoride	mg/l	<0.10
Turbidity	FNU	1.3	Iron (B)	mg/l	<0.05
Turbidity/acidified*	FNU	0.49	Manganese (B)	mg/l	<0.01
Sediments		Little	Calcium (B)	mg/l	3.2
Odour (20°C)		Evident (Musty)	Magnesium (B)	mg/l	0.46
pH		6.5	Total Hardness (B)	°dH	0.55
Conductivity	mS/m	2.5	CO ₂ , aggr. to marble/calc.	mg/l	7
COD _{Mn}	mg/l	1.5	Silica (B)	mg/l	4.0
Ammoniumnitrogen	mg/l	0.03	Potassium (B)	mg/l	0.54
Nitrate-nitrogen	mg/l	0.30	Sodium (B)	mg/l	1.4
Nitrite-nitrogen	mg/l	<0.002	Aluminium (B)	mg/l	0.07
Phosphate-phosphorous	mg/l	0.006	Copper (B)	mg/l	<0.01
Alkalinity	mg HCO ₃ /l	9.4	B: Digestion 0.34 M HNO ₃		-----

* Is not included in the accreditation or has not been performed by VVL.

 Stockholm 21 November, 1997
 Vattenvårdslaboratoriet

Ulla Rydevik

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Appendix D: Structural Data Statistics

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Gneiss	0 of 0	△
Gneiss Unit	0 of 0	△
Magmatic Unit	0 of 0	△
Meta Igneous Unit	54 of 195	△
Metasediments	0 of 0	△
Volcanic Unit	17 of 101	△
Σ	71 of 296	

Small circles:

301° / 41° 6°	———
301° / 41° 22°	———

NORTH ACCESS ROAD TUNNELS

schistosity total north and south tunnel

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Gneiss	0 of	0	△
Gneiss Unit	0 of	0	△
Magmatic Unit	0 of	0	△
Meta Igneous Unit	122 of	195	△
Metasediments	0 of	0	△
Volcanic Unit	55 of	101	△
Σ		177 of	296

NORTH ACCESS ROAD ALIGNMENT WEST

joints Access Road Tunnel north and south

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Gneiss	0 of	0	△
Gneiss Unit	0 of	0	△
Magmatic Unit	0 of	0	△
Meta Igneous Unit	94 of	347	△
Metasediments	36 of	141	△
Volcanic Unit	30 of	169	△
Σ		160 of	657

schistosity total north and south Access Road Tunnel

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Gneiss	0 of	0	△
Gneiss Unit	0 of	0	△
Magmatic Unit	0 of	0	△
Meta Igneous Unit	247 of	347	△
Metasediments	100 of	141	△
Volcanic Unit	137 of	169	△
Σ	484 of	657	

Joint, slickensides, faults west and east alignment

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Gneiss 98 of 98 ◊
Σ 98 of 98

Pol Density:
0,0 % - 4,1 %

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
 Gneiss 98 of 98 ◊
 Σ 98 of 98

Pol Density:
 0,0 % - 4,1 %

Small circles:
 119° / 54° 6° ———
 119° / 54° 12° ———
 161° / 72° 11° ———
 161° / 72° 15° ———
 207° / 75° 11° ———
 207° / 75° 11° ———
 247° / 52° 10° ———
 247° / 52° 13° ———
 305° / 59° 5° ———
 305° / 59° 15° ———

gneiss schistosity and joints

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 470 of 470
 Σ 470 of 470

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○
Σ 0 of 470

magmatic joints Lowari Khwar

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○

Σ 0 of 470

magmatic joints Dare Khwar

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○
Σ 0 of 470

magmatic joints E of Ziarat Post

Lambert projection

Selected classes:

Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○

Σ 0 of 470

joints road to Lowari Tunnel

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○
Σ 0 of 470

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○
Σ 0 of 470

Project: **Lowari**
Diagram: **magmatic joints Lowari Pass**

0.19

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 o
 Σ 0 of 470

magmatics joints Lowari Pass Area

Project: Lowari
Diagram: magmatic joints Mirga Khwar

D-15

Lambert projection

Selected classes:
Magmatic Unit 0 of 470 ○
Σ 0 of 470

magmatic joints Mirga Khwar